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3 1 **Testing polymineral post-IR IRSL and quartz SAR-OSL protocols on Middle to Late**
4 **Pleistocene loess at Batajnica, Serbia**
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12 7
13 7 **Abstract**
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17 9 The loess-paleosol sequence of Batajnica (Vojvodina region, Serbia) is considered
18
19 10 amongst the most complete and thickest terrestrial paleoclimate archive for Middle and Late
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21 11 Pleistocene. In order to achieve a numerical chronology for this profile, four sets of ages were
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23 12 obtained on 18 individual samples. Equivalent doses were determined using the SAR
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25 13 protocol on fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz fractions, as well as on polymineral
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27 14 fine grains by using two elevated temperature infrared stimulation methods, pIRIR₂₉₀ and
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29 15 pIRIR₂₂₅.
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33 16 We show that the upper age limit of coarse quartz OSL and polymineral pIRIR₂₉₀ and
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35 17 pIRIR₂₂₅ techniques is restricted to the Last Glacial Interglacial cycle due to the field
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37 18 saturation of the natural signals. Luminescence ages on coarse quartz, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀
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39 19 polymineral fine grains are in general agreement. Fine quartz ages are systematically lower
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41 20 than the coarse quartz and pIRIR ages, the degree of underestimation increasing with age.
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44 21 Comparison between natural and laboratory dose response curves indicate the age
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46 22 range over which each protocol provides reliable ages. For fine and coarse quartz, the natural
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48 23 and laboratory dose response curves overlap up to ~ 150 Gy and ~250 Gy, respectively
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50 24 suggesting that the SAR protocol provides reliable ages up to ~50 ka on fine quartz and ~100
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52 25 ka on coarse quartz. Using the pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol, equivalent doses up to ~ 400
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54 26 Gy can be determined, beyond which in the case of the former the natural dose response
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56 27 curve slightly overestimates the laboratory dose response curve.
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4 28 Our results suggest that the choice of the mineral and luminescence technique to be
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6 29 used for dating loess sediments should take into consideration the reported limited reliability.

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8 30 **Keywords:** Luminescence dating, quartz, feldspars, loess, Pleistocene

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1. Introduction

The Middle Danube basin comprises several high-resolution Middle-to-Late Pleistocene loess-paleosol sequences (LPS) that document clear similarity in the long-term paleoclimate response between European and Asian loess deposits (Marković et al., 2015 and references therein; Buggle et al., 2009, 2013; Sümeği et al., 2018; Perić et al., 2019). This similarity allowed for inferring common variability in regional atmospheric circulation patterns and dust dynamics driven by glacial-to-interglacial climate variability (e.g. Marković et al., 2015; Zeeden et al., 2018a). However, reliable numerical age constraints for Middle Danube LPS are rare (Stevens et al., 2011; Thiel et al. 2011a; Murray et al., 2014; Böskén et al. 2017; Zhang et al. 2018; Perić et al. 2019). Therefore, the most common approach in deriving chronological frames for Middle Danube LPS relied on correlative techniques based on variability in magnetic susceptibility data (e.g. Marković et al., 2006, 2015, 2018a; Basarin et al., 2014; Zeeden et al., 2018a). Magnetic susceptibility, a proxy for pedogenetic intensity in loess (Zeeden et al., 2018b; Schaetzl et al., 2018) allows for tentatively aligning loess records onto the benthic isotope stack (Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005) or the insolation curve (Laskar et al., 2004).

Luminescence dating is the most applicable method in directly dating the emplacement time of loess forming mineral particles (Roberts, 2008). To date, luminescence dating was applied on quartz and feldspars extracted from Serbian LPS (Fuchs et al., 2008; Stevens et al., 2011; Timar-Gabor et al., 2015; Perić et al., 2019) mainly for records covering the Last Glacial Cycle (LGC). Beyond LGC, only Murray et al. (2014) reported minimum pIRIR₂₉₀ ages for samples found to be in field and laboratory saturation. They determined minimum ages derived from minimum equivalent doses estimates based on an upper limit of 86% of saturation of the laboratory dose response curves.

At the Batajnica LPS (Figure 1) discussed here, five clearly distinguishable loess and paleosol units are exposed, reaching to Marine Isotope Stage (MIS) 16 and possibly beyond

92 (Marković et al., 2009). Despite the importance of Batajnica LPS as a terrestrial
93 paleoclimate record for the Middle Danube loess field, no numerical ages have been reported
94 so far.

95 Here we provide (i) a detailed multi-method luminescence chronology for Batajnica
96 profile with the focus on the last glacial loess unit to (ii) explore the upper dating limit of the
97 single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) protocol applied on 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz
98 OSL, as well as pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ applied on 4-11 μm polymineral fine grains from
99 samples collected from L1 (c. MIS 5-2) loess unit and at the lower boundaries of S1 (c. MIS
100 5), S2 (c. MIS 7) and S3 (c. MIS 9) paleosols; and (iii) compare the natural and laboratory
101 generated quartz SAR-OSL and post-IR IRSL₂₂₅ and IRSL₂₉₀ dose response curves and thus
102 assess what is the dose range over which each protocol provides reliable ages.

103 2. Sampling and site description

104 Batajnica LPS is located along the Danube, near Batajnica settlement, 15 km
105 northwest of Belgrade (44°55'29''N; 20°19'11''E) (Figure 1). The composite Batajnica LPS
106 previously investigated by Marković et al. (2009) reaches a thickness of 40 m. The section
107 comprises at least five loess-paleosol couplets, extending to or beyond 600 ka (Figure 2).
108 Two visible dark-brown (altered) volcanic ash layers have been documented in loess unit L2
109 (Figure 2). Previous studies on Batajnica include pedostratigraphical correlations,
110 rubification index and environmental magnetic data (Marković et al., 2009). A relative
111 chronology has been obtained by correlating the magnetic susceptibility record with Lingtai
112 (Chinese Loess Plateau) and the SPECMAP oxygen isotope record (Marković et al., 2009).

113 Luminescence investigations were carried out on 18 individual samples collected in
114 stainless steel tubes from the same outcrops studied by Marković et al. (2009). Seven
115 samples were taken from L1 loess unit. Doublet samples were collected from the lower
116 boundaries of S1, S2 and S3 paleosols, and one sample from the upper boundary of S2

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3 117 paleosol. Additionally, four samples were taken to assess the chronological range of the L2
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5 118 tephra layers (**Figure 2**).

119 **3. Methodology**

120 **3.1 Sample preparation and analytical facilities**

121 The luminescence samples were prepared under low intensity red light conditions.
122 Gamma spectrometry and water content measurements were carried out using material from
123 the ends of each sample tube, whereas fine quartz (4-11 μm), coarse quartz (63-90 μm) and
124 polymineral fine grains were extracted from the inner part. A treatment with hydrochloric
125 acid (10% concentration) was employed for calcium carbonate removal followed by a
126 treatment with hydrogen peroxide (10% concentration followed by 30%) for organic matter
127 removal. Finer (<63 μm) and coarser (>63 μm) grains were separated through wet sieving.
128 Fine grains (<11 μm) were obtained by settling using Stokes' law. The quartz fraction was
129 enriched by etching with hydrofluorosilicic acid for 10 days. The 4-11 μm quartz fraction
130 was obtained by centrifugation in distilled water. Polymineral fine grains (4-11 μm) were
131 separated from the finer polymineral fraction obtained after Stokes law settling and
132 centrifuging in distilled water (**Frechen et al., 1996; Lang et al., 1996**). Coarser (63-90 μm)
133 grains fraction was separated through dry sieving. Since this fraction consists of a
134 polymineral mixture, a density separation using heavy liquid was performed (2.62 g/cm^3 and
135 2.75 g/cm^3). To isolate the quartz grains from the plagioclase feldspars, a treatment with
136 hydrofluoric acid (40% concentration) was applied for 40 minutes. A rinse with hydrochloric
137 acid (10%) for 60 minutes removed the precipitated fluorides. For measurement, fine quartz
138 and polymineral grains were mounted on aluminium disks whereas for coarse grains stainless
139 steel disks were used.

140 Luminescence measurements were performed using TL/OSL Risø DA-20 readers,
141 equipped with classic or automated detection and stimulation head (DASH) (**Lapp et al.,**

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3 142 **2015**). Luminescence signals were detected by EMI 9235QA and a PDM 9107Q-AP-TTL-03
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5 143 (160-630 nm) photomultipliers. 7.5 mm thick Hoya U-340 UV filters were used for the
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7 144 detection of the quartz signals while for polymineral fine grains signals a blue filter
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9 145 combination (Schott BG39 + Corning 7-59, with transmission between 320-460 nm) was
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11 146 used. Laboratory irradiations were carried out using ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y radioactive sources that were
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13 147 calibrated with gamma-irradiated calibration quartz (**Hansen et al., 2015**) for both fine and
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15 148 coarse grain fractions. The dose rate used for measurements was 0.11 Gy/s for fine grains and
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17 149 0.13 Gy/s for coarse grains.
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22 150 The bleaching experiments on polymineral fine grains were carried out under
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24 151 controlled laboratory conditions using an array of TL29D16/09N lamps which deliver a
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26 152 power of approximately 1000 W/m² with similar spectral characteristics as the natural
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28 153 sunlight (**Petrušić et al., 2011**). We have assumed that one day of exposure to this lamp
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30 154 corresponds to one day of exposure to natural daylight during summer time.
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33 155 **3.2 Equivalent dose determination**

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35 156 Equivalent doses of fine (4-11 μm) and coarse (63-90 μm) quartz grains were
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37 157 determined using the single-aliquot regenerative dose (SAR) procedure (**Murray and**
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39 158 **Wintle, 2000, 2003**). Full details on each protocol are given in **Table S1**. Optical stimulation
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41 159 was carried out with blue light emitting diodes for 40 s at 125 °C. The net CW-OSL signal
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43 160 used for analysis was integrated over the first 0.308 s of the decay curve minus an early
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45 161 background subtraction from 1.69 – 2.30 s interval. Sensitivity changes were corrected by
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47 162 using the OSL response to a test dose of 17 Gy throughout the whole set of measurements. A
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49 163 preheat temperature of 220 °C for 10 s and a cutheat of 180 °C were employed. A high
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51 164 temperature bleach of 280 °C for 40 s was performed at the end of each SAR cycle (**Murray**
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53 165 **and Wintle, 2003**). The robustness of the SAR protocol was checked by the intrinsic
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55 166 performance tests (recycling and recuperation) (**Murray and Wintle, 2003**) included in
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3 167 every measurement. OSL IR depletion tests were performed in order to investigate the purity
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5 168 of the quartz luminescence signals on all aliquots measured (**Duller, 2003**). For equivalent
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8 169 dose determination, only the aliquots that yielded recycling and OSL IR depletion ratios
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10 170 within 10% deviation from unity were accepted. Recuperation signal was considered suitable
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12 171 for less than 2% of the natural signal.

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14 172 Two elevated temperature infrared stimulation methods based on the SAR procedure
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16 173 were used for measuring the polymineral fine grains. We first applied post-IR IRSL protocol
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18 174 (pIRIR₂₉₀) on all samples from Batajnica LPS (see **Table S1b**) (**Thiel et al., 2011a; Buylaert**
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20 175 **et al., 2011b, 2012**). After a preheat of 320 °C for 60 s, the samples were exposed to IR
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22 176 diodes for 200 s at 50 °C in order to reduce the signal which is prone to fading by allowing
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24 177 recombination of near-neighbour trap and centre pairs. The signal of interest was recorded
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26 178 during a subsequent IR stimulation at 290 °C for 200 s. A test dose of 17 Gy was used in all
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28 179 measurements, unless otherwise stated. The net signal used for analysis was integrated from
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30 180 the initial ~2.5 s of stimulation minus a background from the last 50 s. At the end of every
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32 181 cycle, a high-temperature bleach was performed for 100 s at 325 °C to remove residual
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34 182 charge.

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36 183 A further post-IR IRSL protocol (pIRIR₂₂₅) (see **Table S1c**) (**Roberts., 2008;**
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38 184 **Buylaert et al., 2009; Wacha and Frechen 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012**) was employed to
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40 185 determine equivalent doses on samples previously measured with pIRIR₂₉₀, in order to check
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42 186 the reliability of the pIRIR₂₉₀ ages. After a preheat of 250 °C for 60 s, the aliquots were
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44 187 stimulated with IR diodes, firstly at 50 °C for 200 s and then at 225 °C for 200 s. The signal
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46 188 from the latter stimulation was used in equivalent dose determination. The response to a test
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48 189 dose of 17 Gy was determined in the same way. In the end of each cycle of the protocol,
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50 190 bleach at 290 °C for 100 s was performed.

51 191 **3.3 Annual dose determination**

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3 192 High-resolution gamma spectrometry was applied for determining the radionuclide
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5 193 activity concentrations using a well-type HPGe detector. In order to achieve ^{226}Ra - ^{222}Rn
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7 194 equilibrium, the samples were stored for one month. The activity of ^{238}U was determined
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9 195 indirectly by measuring the ^{234}Th emissions of 92.3 keV and 92.8 keV peaks. The ^{226}Ra
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11 196 activity was determined from the emissions at 295 keV and 351 keV of ^{214}Pb and the
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13 197 emission at 609 keV of ^{214}Bi . The activity of the ^{232}Th was determined indirectly by
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15 198 measuring the following peaks: 338 keV (^{228}Ac), 911 keV (^{228}Ac), 238 keV (^{212}Pb) and 583
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17 199 keV (^{208}Tl). For determination of the ^{40}K activity, the 1461 keV peak was used. The annual
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19 200 dose rates were determined using the conversion factors tabulated by **Guérin et al. (2011)**.
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21 201 The beta attenuation and etching factor for 63-90 μm quartz fraction was assumed to be
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23 202 0.94 ± 0.05 (**Mejdahl, 1979**). For the 4-11 μm quartz fraction, an alpha efficiency factor of
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25 203 0.04 ± 0.02 was taken into account whereas for the polymineral fine grains a value of
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27 204 0.08 ± 0.02 was used (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). The time averaged water content was assumed to be
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29 205 15% with a relative error of 25% based on the average humidity of the loess samples in
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31 206 Vojvodina. The external contribution from beta and gamma radiation (additionally alpha
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33 207 radiation for 4-11 μm grains), as well as from the cosmic ray was included in the total dose
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35 208 rates. For each sample, the dose rate of cosmic ray was estimated as function of depth,
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37 209 altitude and geomagnetic latitude (**Prescott and Hutton, 1994**). The internal dose rate
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39 210 contribution for the coarse quartz fraction was assumed to be 0.010 ± 0.002 Gy/ka
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41 211 (**Vandenberghé et al., 2008**). Given the size of fine grains (4-11 μm), it is assumed that any
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43 212 dose rate derived from internal alpha activity is negligibly small.
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51 213 Additionally, the total ^{210}Pb content was determined for ten samples by measuring the
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53 214 concentration of ^{210}Po (5.304 keV peak, alpha energy) by means of alpha spectrometry. A
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55 215 chemical separation was performed on the loess matrix for isolating the Po isotopes from the
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57 216 other alpha emitters (details in the Supplementary material). The measurements were carried
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3 217 out using an ORTEC SOLOIST 450 mm² PIPS detector (19 keV resolutions) and an ASPEC-
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8 219 **3.4 Determination of expected ages for the major paleosol units based on** 9 10 220 **magnetic susceptibility correlation**

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12 221 **Marković et al. (2009)** described the characteristic stratigraphical pattern in magnetic
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14 222 susceptibility for the uppermost soil and various paleosol units at Batajnica and how it can be
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16 223 correlated with similar records throughout Eurasia. It is well known that major paleosols
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18 224 within Eurasian LPSs exhibit a distinctive magnetic enhancement pattern, which is also
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20 225 reflected in grain size and colour proxies, and denoting the degree of pedogenesis which in
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22 226 turn is hydroclimatically controlled. These patterns and their stratigraphical superposition
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24 227 allow for secure identification of major paleosols and serve as independent
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26 228 chronostratigraphical markers that constitute the backbone of the loess chronostratigraphy in
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28 229 the wider Danube Basin and beyond (**Marković et al., 2015; Necula et al., 2015**). Starting
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30 230 from this well established base, **Basarin et al. (2014)** correlated the astronomically tuned
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32 231 magnetic susceptibility record of Titel/Stari Slankamen composite profile to the benthic
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34 232 oxygen isotope stack (**Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005**) for the last ~ 800 ka.

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39 233 As such, the major loess-paleosol transitions identified in Batajnica according to the
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41 234 magnetic susceptibility record were correlated to the corresponding ones in the Titel/Stari
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43 235 Slankamen composite profile (**Figure 2**). This approach (see **Basarin et al., 2014**) further
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45 236 enabled a correlation to the benthic oxygen isotope stack (**Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005**). As
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47 237 the luminescence samples were collected from the same outcrop where the magnetic
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49 238 susceptibility samples were taken, previous field marks allowed for secure correlation of our
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51 239 samples and the magnetic susceptibility samples. Expected age estimates have been assigned
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53 240 to samples collected from the Holocene soil and paleosols boundaries (BAT-1.0, 1.11, 1.12A,
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3 241 1.16, 1.17 and 1.19A) based on the data reported from **Basarin et al. (2014)** and their
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5 242 correlation to benthic oxygen ages of **Lisiecki and Raymo (2005)** (**Figure 2; Table S2**).

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7 243 This method of determining expected ages relies on the assumption that no large
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9 244 erosional gaps occur at the loess-paleosol transitions for Batajnica and Titel/Stari Slankamen.
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11 245 We are confident that this assumption is valid for the investigated sites as the regional
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13 246 Danube Basin stratigraphy is very well constrained by integrating many profiles; in case a
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15 247 significant erosional gap occurs (e.g. Stari Slankamen L2), it can be clearly identified even
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17 248 for loess units (**Marković et al. 2009; 2015**). Smaller erosion gaps cannot be excluded, but
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19 249 they are not relevant at the time scale of the uncertainties in the expected depositional ages.
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21 250 Furthermore, in order to account for possible uncertainties, a 10% error has been associated
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23 251 with the boundary ages between loess and soil or paleosols.

24 252 **4. Results and discussion**

25 253 **4.1 Annual doses and calculation of expected equivalent doses**

26 254 **Tables 1 and S3** contain relevant information on dosimetry and specific radionuclide
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28 255 activities. The annual doses were derived from the activity concentrations of the ^{238}U , ^{232}Th
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30 256 ^{40}K and ^{210}Pb measured using gamma spectrometry.

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32 257 We have investigated the secular equilibrium assumption in the ^{238}U chain by
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34 258 assessing the ratio between the activity concentration of ^{210}Pb measured directly using the 46
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36 259 keV line and ^{226}Ra indirectly measured using the ^{214}Pb (352 keV and 295 keV) and ^{214}Bi
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38 260 (609.3 keV) energy peaks. The average ratio calculated on all samples is 0.48 ± 0.03 (**Figure**
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40 261 **S1**). This is caused either by the escape of the ^{222}Rn during burial time or by inaccurate
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42 262 gamma spectrometry measurement of ^{210}Pb . Thus, the activity concentration of ^{210}Pb was
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44 263 determined indirectly using alpha spectrometry by measuring ^{210}Po on ten samples. As seen
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46 264 in **Figure S2**, the ratios between the alpha and gamma spectrometry results are consistent
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48 265 with unity, showing that the activity concentrations of ^{210}Pb obtained by gamma spectrometry
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3 266 are accurately determined. This indicates that ca. 50% radon loss occurs in the investigated
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5 267 loess samples. Thus the annual doses that consider the measured ^{210}Pb were used in
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8 268 determining the luminescence ages.

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10 269 By multiplying the expected age estimates (**Table S2**) with the corresponding
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12 270 environmental dose rate expected equivalent doses and their associated uncertainties were
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15 271 determined (**Table S2**).

17 272 **4.2 Luminescence properties - Quartz**

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19 273 For both quartz fractions the net signals displayed a rapid decay during optical
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21 274 stimulation as documented for sample BAT-1.10 in **Figure S3**. The pattern of the natural and
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24 275 regenerative decay curve was found to be similar with that shown by the luminescence signal
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26 276 of the calibration quartz, which is recognised as being dominated by the fast component
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28 277 (**Hansen et al., 2015**). Representative laboratory growth curves are shown in **Figure S3**,
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31 278 displaying a good behaviour in the SAR protocol. The dose response curves were well fitted
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33 279 using the sum of two saturating exponential functions. The recycling and IR depletion ratios
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35 280 were within 10% from unity, demonstrating that the sensitivity changes during repeated SAR
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38 281 cycles are accurately corrected for, and the quartz signals are pure (**Table S3**).

40 282 *Preheat plateau*

41
42 283 The dependency of the equivalent doses on the preheat temperature was investigated
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44 284 for sample BAT-1.13B (fine quartz). Different preheat temperatures ranging from 180 °C to
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47 285 280 °C were applied on sets of five aliquots for each sample, in combination with test dose
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49 286 cutheat of 180°C. **Figure S4** shows that over the investigated interval of preheat
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51 287 temperatures, equivalent doses do not display systematic variation. The recycling ratio and
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54 288 recuperation were satisfactory for all the aliquots measured.

56 289 *Dose recovery*

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3 290 Further investigation was focused on analysing whether the SAR protocol can
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5 291 successfully measure a known irradiation dose prior to any thermal treatment by applying the
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8 292 dose recovery test (Murray and Wintle, 2003). Sets of five aliquots were prepared from 4-
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10 293 11 μm quartz samples (BAT-1.9, 1.11, 1.12B, 1.13B) and 63-90 μm quartz samples (BAT-
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12 294 1.1, 1.9, 1.11, 1.12B). The aliquots were irradiated with a beta dose, chosen to approximate
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15 295 the equivalent doses, after their natural signals were bleached by a repeated exposure to the
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17 296 blue light emitting diodes for 100 s at room temperature with a pause of 10 ks. These doses
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19 297 were then determined using SAR protocol. As seen in **Figure 3A**, for the quartz samples, the
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21 298 SAR protocol can successfully recover laboratory doses up to 320 Gy on fine quartz and 260
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24 299 Gy on coarse quartz.

300 *Quartz equivalent doses*

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28 301 Equivalent doses were measured on at least 10 aliquots of each grain size. **Table 1**
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30 302 and **Table S3** summarize the equivalent dose results, as well as the results from the SAR-
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32 303 intrinsic tests (Recycling, IR depletion and Recuperation).

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35 304 Equivalent doses measured on fine quartz aliquots range from 31 ± 1 Gy for sample
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37 305 BAT-1.0 collected from the Holocene soil to 486 ± 5 Gy for sample BAT-1.19A from below
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39 306 S3 paleosol. The natural signal emitted by this sample interpolates well below the laboratory
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42 307 saturation threshold. Yet, the measured fine quartz equivalent dose reaches only 50% of the
43
44 308 expected burial dose (**Table S2**). Coarse quartz equivalent doses range from 28 ± 1 Gy for the
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46 309 sample from modern soil to 262 ± 16 Gy for a sample collected below the S1 paleosol. For
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48 310 older samples, the natural signal was in field saturation and close to laboratory saturation
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50 311 (more detailed discussion in **Section 4.5**).

51 52 53 312 **4.3 Luminescence properties - Polymineral fine grains**

54
55 313 **Figures S3 C-D** show representative growth curves for sample BAT-1.10 constructed
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57 314 using pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ protocols. The dose response curves were well fitted using a sum
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3 315 of two saturating exponential functions. The growth curves pass very close to the origin
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5 316 demonstrating that the recuperation is insignificant. As can be seen in insets of the **Figure S3**
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7 317 **C-D** the decays with stimulation time of the natural and regenerative signals have similar
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9 318 shape.

319 *Effect of test dose size on equivalent dose*

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14 320 The effect of test dose size on the measured equivalent dose using the pIRIR₂₉₀
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16 321 protocol has been investigated on samples BAT-1.9, 1.12A and 1.16 (**Figure 4**). Sets of three
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18 322 to five aliquots were used for each test dose (except for 17 Gy test dose). As shown in **Figure**
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20 323 **4** for samples BAT-1.9 and BAT-1.12A no systematic trend in equivalent dose values with
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22 324 test dose magnitude can be seen. Although not so clear, this is valid for sample BAT-1.16
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24 325 that yielded pIRIR₂₉₀ equivalent doses of 1172±129 Gy and 996±64 Gy by employing test
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26 326 dose sizes of 2% and 50% of the De, respectively. The expected equivalent dose for sample
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28 327 BAT-1.16 is 617±84 Gy (**Table S2**). It is important to note that the natural signal emitted by
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30 328 sample BAT-1.16 normalized to a test dose of 17 Gy was interpolated in the saturation region
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32 329 of the dose response curve. The results on Batajnica loess samples indicate that the
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34 330 dependence of the equivalent dose on the size of test dose, supported by investigations in
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36 331 Chinese loess (**Yi et al., 2016**), might not be a general phenomenon.

332 *Determination of residual doses*

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334 One of the most important assumptions of the luminescence dating method is that the
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336 luminescence signal of the mineral has been fully reset in nature by light exposure prior to
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338 deposition. The aeolian nature of loess deposits ensures us that the mineral constituents have
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340 experienced considerable daylight exposure. **Buylaert et al. (2012)** showed that PIRIR
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342 signals bleach at a much slower rate than the quartz OSL signal. For pIRIR₂₂₅ signals emitted
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344 by K-feldspar residual doses of a not exceeding 2 Gy were reported (**e.g. Buylaert et al.,**
345
346 **2009**). But later on, hard-to-bleach (or un-bleachable) pIRIR signals amounting to ~ 6 Gy
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3 340 have been reported for K-feldspar extracts from Chinese Loess after extensive exposure in
4
5 341 solar simulator (Yi et al., 2016). Bleaching experiments conducted by Stevens et al. (2011)
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7 342 on polymineral fine grains from loess collected from the Carpathian Basin suggest that the
8
9 343 value of the residual is influenced by the exposure time and conditions as well as the
10
11 344 equivalent dose of the sample with residual values for pIRIR₂₉₀ signals ranging from 5.5 Gy
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13 345 (for 28 days exposure outside of a sample taken from S0/L1 boundary) to 33 Gy (in the case
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15 346 of a sample taken from L2 that was exposed to window light for 8 days).
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19 347 Besides conducting laboratory bleaching experiments another way to derive the
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21 348 residual doses is by measuring a modern analogue, which is a modern sample. Buylaert et
22
23 349 al., 2011a carried such a study on 3 samples of modern dust and 3 samples with equivalent
24
25 350 doses of less than 1 Gy collected from the Chinese Loess Plateau. A residual average dose of
26
27 351 4 Gy was obtained for pIRIR₂₂₅ signals while a higher average value of 11 Gy was reported
28
29 352 in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀ signals.
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33 353 Due to the complexity of bleaching behaviour of feldspar signals, as explained above,
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35 354 in this study we have conducted residual doses corrections both by laboratory measurements
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37 355 of the residuals as well as by using the modern analogue approach.
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40 356 Three to five aliquots were used for residual dose measurement. Fresh disks were
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42 357 exposed for 1 month to the UV lamp before the doses measurement. The measured residual
43
44 358 values amount to maximum of 0.5% and 4% of the measured pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀
45
46 359 equivalent doses, respectively (Table S5 and S6). Similar pIRIR₂₂₅ residual doses (after
47
48 360 laboratory bleaching) have been reported by Wacha and Frechen (2011) for loess
49
50 361 samples collected from Gorjanović site near Vukovar, Croatia. Our pIRIR₂₉₀ residual results
51
52 362 are consistent with those obtained by Constantin et al. (2019) for loess samples from
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54 363 Mošorin (Vojvodina, Serbia) and Veres et al. (2018) for Stayky LPS, Ukraine. It is important
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56 364 to note that in this study the size of the residual doses does not vary with age.
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3 365 As there was no true modern analogue at our disposal we have estimated the values
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5 366 for the residuals by using the young samples where age control is available as follows. We
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7 367 estimated the residual doses by comparing the polymineral ages with the average fine and
8
9 368 coarse quartz age of the uppermost sample BAT-1.0. Quartz ages obtained for this sample are
10
11 369 in excellent agreement with independent age control (11.5 ± 1 ka, **Table S2**) based on
12
13 370 magnetic susceptibility correlation. The age offset was converted into residual dose using the
14
15 371 annual dose rate determined for each sample. These residual doses were subtracted from all
16
17 372 the pIRIR D_e values prior to calculation of the ages (**Table 1**).

373 *Dose recovery*

374 Dose recovery test (**Murray, 1996; Wallinga et al., 2000**) was performed on five
375 aliquots from samples BAT-1.8 to 1.11 and BAT-1.12B. The natural signal was bleached by
376 exposing fresh aliquots to lamp for 2 weeks. Laboratory known doses were chosen to match
377 the measured equivalent dose. The residual doses were subtracted from the recovered doses
378 before calculating the dose recovery ratios. Unless otherwise stated, a test dose of 17 Gy was
379 used throughout the measurements. As shown in **Figure 3B** the pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol can
380 successfully recover laboratory doses up to 316 Gy, while the pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol
381 systematically overestimates the given laboratory doses. Following the suggestions of **Yi et**
382 **al. (2016)** we have carried out pIRIR₂₉₀ dose recovery tests using higher test doses. For
383 sample BAT-1.9, the dose recovery ratio improved from 1.36 ± 0.06 to 1.07 ± 0.03 using a 17
384 Gy test dose (7% of D_e) and a 50 Gy test dose (23% of D_e), respectively. However, for
385 sample BAT-1.11 poor dose recovery ratios of 1.31 ± 0.04 and 1.41 ± 0.10 were obtained by
386 using test doses of 17 Gy (5% of D_e) and 150 Gy (41% of D_e). As shown above, the size of
387 the test dose does not influence the measured equivalent dose (**Figure 4**) or the saturation
388 characteristics of the pIRIR₂₉₀ dose response curves (see **Section 4.5.1**). Thus, in this paper
389 we will discuss the equivalent doses measured with a test dose of 17 Gy.

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390 Unsatisfactory dose recovery tests for pIRIR₂₉₀ have also been reported by **Murray et**
391 **al. (2014)** for Serbian loess, by **Veres et al. (2018)** for Ukrainian loess, and by **Thiel et al.**
392 **(2011b)** for Japanese loess. On fluvial and lacustrine sediments from Heidelberg Basin,
393 Germany, **Li et al. (2018)** reported poor pIRIR₂₉₀ dose recovery and good pIRIR₂₂₅ dose
394 recovery. However, such behaviour is not general since **Thiel et al. (2011a)**, **Yi et al., (2016)**,
395 **Bösken et al. (2017)**, **Stevens et al. (2018)** and **Zhang et al. (2018)** reported good pIRIR₂₉₀
396 dose recovery ratios for the loess in the Middle Danube basin and the Chinese Loess Plateau.

397 *Polymineral fine grains equivalent doses*

398 The pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ equivalent doses after the subtraction of residual doses are
399 displayed in **Table 1** while the measured equivalent doses are presented in **Table S4**. The
400 pIRIR₂₉₀ equivalent doses vary from 36±9 Gy (BAT-1.0) to 490±21 Gy (BAT-1.12A). The
401 smallest pIRIR₂₂₅ equivalent dose is 37±6 Gy (BAT-1.0), whereas the maximum is 377±19
402 Gy (BAT-1.12A).

403 The natural pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ signals yielded by older samples scatter around or
404 above the saturation threshold of the dose response curve (see **Section 4.5**).

405 *Fading rates measurements for high doses*

406 While pIRIR₂₂₅ fading rates > 1%/decade are reported in the literature (**Thomsen et**
407 **al., 2008; Buylaert et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2018)**, **Vasiliniuc et al. (2012)** calculated
408 fading rates ranging from 0.6 to 1.3%/decade on samples collected from the Last Glacial
409 loess in Mircea-Voda, Romania and concluded they are laboratory artefacts. **Stevens et al.**
410 **(2011)**, **Thiel et al. (2011a)** and **Murray et al. (2014)** reported fading rates considered to be
411 laboratory artefacts for polymineral pIRIR₂₉₀ signals on Serbian and Austrian loess sites
412 along the Danube valley. **Balescu et al. (in press)** determined extremely low fading rates
413 (<0.18%/decade) for pIRIR₂₉₀ signals emitted by K-feldspars extracted from Bulgarian loess.

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3 414 Fading rates (percentage of the signal lost per decade of time **Aitken (1985)**) were
4
5 415 measured on fresh 4-11 μm polymineral aliquots from sample BAT-1.11 and BAT-1.19A
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7 416 (**Figure S5** and **Table S7**). The aliquots were bleached by exposure to lamp for 2 weeks and
8
9 417 irradiated with beta doses approximating the equivalent dose (317 Gy and 364 Gy) for BAT-
10
11 418 1.11 and 400 Gy for BAT-1.19A, respectively. A test dose of a magnitude of 17 Gy was used
12
13 419 throughout all fading measurements. A number of four consecutive prompt read-outs were
14
15 420 carried out before fading measurement. The aliquots were preheated before storage.
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17 421 Following the readout after different storage times, two consecutive prompt readouts were
18
19 422 carried out.

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22
23 423 **Figure S5 (A-L)** shows a significant scatter in the pIRIR sensitivity corrected
24
25 424 luminescence signals registered during prompt read-outs. It is interesting to note that the
26
27 425 signal intensity recorded after the first instantaneous readout always lies above the values
28
29 426 recorded during the subsequent prompt readouts. We consider that no systematic variation
30
31 427 with delay time is identified for the pIRIR sensitivity corrected luminescence signals.

32
33 428 The luminescence stability of the quartz is well known, and previous studies reported
34
35 429 that the quartz signal is not thought to suffer from anomalous fading (**Aitken, 1998**). Though,
36
37 430 **Thiel et al. (2011a)** reported fading rates of 1.3 ± 0.3 %/decade for fine quartz extracted from
38
39 431 Chinese loess. Fading tests were also performed by **Lowick et al. (2018)** on fine and coarse
40
41 432 quartz. They determined quartz *g*-values ranging from 0 to 6 %/decade while for calibration
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43 433 quartz *g*-values of 1-2 %/decade were measured.

44
45 434 We performed fading measurements on 4-11 quartz and 63-90 μm quartz extracted
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47 435 from sample BAT-1.11 in order to test whether the calculated *g*-values on polymineral
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49 436 material are fitting artefacts caused by large scatter in the dataset. The aliquots were bleached
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51 437 twice with blue LEDs for 100 s at room temperature. Between the two stimulations, a pause
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53 438 of 10 ks was used. After bleaching, the *g*-values were measured using SAR-OSL protocol in
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3 439 the same manner as polymineral fine grains. **Figure S5 (M-S)** shows that the scatter in the
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5 440 quartz data is comparable with the polymineral dataset. We report average g-values of $2.49 \pm$
6
7 441 0.44 %/decade and 2.92 ± 0.61 %/decade for 4-11 μm quartz and 63-90 μm quartz, respectively
8
9 442 (**Table S7**). Such g-values cannot reflect real fading as this would imply a significant signal
10
11 443 loss during burial. This is in contradiction with our observation that the natural signals
12
13 444 emitted by 63-90 μm quartz are close to full saturation, as discussed later on in **Section 4.5.1**.

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17 445 We interpret the presented dataset as follows. There is no solid evidence that quartz
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19 446 and pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ polymineral signals fade, but rather that by using this procedure,
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21 447 on the investigated samples, one cannot measure reliable g-values. Since we cannot
22
23 448 confidently measure g-values using the short term standard fading measurement procedures
24
25 449 in the following we discuss the uncorrected pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages for samples BAT-1.0
26
27 450 –BAT 1.12B. One should also note that fading corrections shall not be attempted if the
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29 451 natural signal interpolates beyond the linear range of the dose response curve, as it is the case
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31 452 with most of the natural signals emitted from Batajnica samples (**Huntley and Lamothe,**
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33 453 **2001**).

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37 454 *High laboratory doses given on top of naturally accrued doses*

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39 455 Previous studies reported a mismatch between SAR dose response curves and the
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41 456 dose response curve constructed when large doses were added on top of natural for fine and
42
43 457 coarse quartz, indicating that the SAR-OSL protocol is problematic in the high dose range.
44
45 458 **Anechitei-Deacu et al. (2018)** showed that in the case of fine quartz extracted from
46
47 459 aeolianites the sensitivity corrected luminescence signal after a large dose was added on top
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49 460 of natural was not found to be at the same level to the laboratory saturation region, reaching
50
51 461 only 86% of SAR laboratory full saturation intensity, while in the case of coarse quartz 96%
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53 462 of full saturation has been attained. On quartz extracted from Ukrainian loess, **Veres et al.**
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55 463 (**2018**) showed that after adding 3500 Gy on top of the natural signal of 4-11 μm quartz
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3 464 (De~550 Gy), the sensitivity corrected signal reached 96% of the of the luminescence level
4
5 465 induced by a 4000 Gy beta dose. In the case of 63-90 μm fraction identical luminescence
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7 466 levels were measured after adding 500 Gy beta dose on top of the natural signal (De ~ 500
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9
10 467 Gy) and after a 1000 Gy beta dose.

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12 468 If on samples for which natural signals were found in field saturation are added large
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14 469 laboratory doses, an increase of the signals may suggest a degree of fading that may have
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16
17 470 been undetected during standard fading rates measurements. On the other hand, if a large
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19 471 dose is given on top of the naturally accrued doses, one normally expects the magnitude of
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21 472 the measured signal to be the same as the saturation value measured in the SAR protocol.

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24 473 We have chosen to perform such an experiment on sample BAT-1.19A, collected
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26 474 below S3 paleosol. As it can be seen in **Figure 7a** in the case of polymineral fine grains the
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28 475 natural signals of this sample with an expected age of more than 300 ka reaches $84\pm 1\%$ of
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30 476 saturation level for pIRIR₂₂₅ while for pIRIR₂₉₀ the signal lies above the laboratory dose
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32 477 response curve ($105\pm 3\%$). For quartz natural sensitivity corrected signals are at $95\pm 6\%$ of
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34 478 laboratory saturation levels in the case of 63-90 μm grains, while in the case of fine grains
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36 479 only $56\pm 1\%$ of saturation level is reached.

37
38
39 480 A number of 10 aliquots of these samples were prepared for each measurement
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41 481 protocol. The first five aliquots were used as control aliquots for recording the natural signals
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43 482 (L_n/T_n), while the rest of the aliquots were irradiated to a beta dose added on top of the
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45 483 naturally accrued dose. The magnitude of this dose was chosen to be large enough for the
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47 484 signal to reach full saturation (see **Figure 7a**). The sensitivity corrected luminescence signal
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49 485 (denoted as $(L_n/T_n)^*$) was recorded after the large dose was added. The same aliquots were
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51 486 subsequently measured in a standard SAR protocol after an irradiation to a dose of 5000 Gy,
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53 487 chosen to equal the equivalent dose plus the given dose. The value of this normalised signal
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55 488 is hereafter denoted as (L_x/T_x) .

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3 489 If $(L_n/T_n)^*$ is greater than (L_n/T_n) there is the possibility that during burial time some
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5 490 loss of the signal may have occurred. In addition, if $(L_n/T_n)^*$ is greater or smaller than
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7 491 (L_x/T_x) , issues regarding unknown measurement problems during the first cycle of the
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9 492 measurement or other yet unknown causes can also be suspected.

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12 493 From **Table S10** it can be seen that for quartz the ratio between $(L_n/T_n)^*$ and (L_n/T_n)
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14 494 is 1.90 ± 0.02 in the case of fine grains and 0.96 ± 0.08 in the case of coarse grains,
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16 495 respectively. For polymineral fine grains the ratio of $(L_n/T_n)^*$ to (L_n/T_n) is 1.35 ± 0.03 in the
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18 496 case of pIRIR₂₂₅ and 1.20 ± 0.04 in the case of pIRIR₂₉₀, respectively. The ratio between
19
20 497 $(L_n/T_n)^*$ and (L_x/T_x) in the case of pIRIR₂₂₅ is 1.10 ± 0.03 while for pIRIR₂₉₀ is 1.15 ± 0.05 .
21
22 498 While in the case of fine and coarse quartz corresponding ratios of 0.95 ± 0.02 and 1.03 ± 0.11 ,
23
24 499 respectively were obtained (**Table S10**).

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26
27 500 This indicates that in the case of all signals excepting coarse quartz OSL the
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29 501 maximum light levels attained during prolonged natural irradiation can be increased by
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31 502 additional laboratory irradiation. We choose to restrain ourselves from interpreting this
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33 503 observation as an indicator of signal fading during burial because our results here as well as
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35 504 those obtained in fading tests indicate that it is likely that the signals measured during the first
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37 505 measurement cycle in pIRIR protocols slightly overestimate the response obtained for the
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39 506 same dose later given in the SAR protocol. The cause of this behaviour needs further
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41 507 investigation.

47 508 **4.4 Luminescence ages**

48
49 509 The ages calculated using the measured activity concentrations of ^{210}Pb are generally
50
51 510 10 to 20% older than those calculated assuming secular equilibrium in the ^{238}U chain, but the
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53 511 two sets of ages are consistent within error limits (**Figure S6**). Assuming a constant radon
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55 512 loss over the whole sample burial time, the set of ages calculated using the measured activity
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57 513 concentrations of ^{210}Pb are discussed in the following section.

1
2
3 514 **Table 1** display the 4-11 μm quartz, 63-90 μm quartz, pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅
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5
6 515 polymineral ages assumed to be unaffected by fading and by considering two possibility for
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8 516 residual dose correction namely by using the values obtained by laboratory bleaching
9
10 517 experiments and by considering residuals derived through the use of a modern analogue.
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12 518 Only the ages obtained by using the latter correction procedure are discussed further on.

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15 519 For Batajnica, the luminescence ages are in agreement with the previous
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17 520 chronological framework based on magnetic susceptibility correlation to other records
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19 521 (**Buggle et al., 2009; Marković et al., 2009**), placing the L1 loess unit into the Last Glacial.

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21
22 522 Except for sample BAT-1.9, all fine quartz ages are systematically lower than coarse
23
24 523 quartz ages and the difference between them increases with depth (**Figure 5**), with the fine
25
26 524 quartz underestimating the expected depositional ages based on magnetic stratigraphy
27
28 525 (**Figure 6**). At the neighbouring Titel loess section, **Perić et al. (2019)** reported unreliable
29
30 526 fine quartz ages beyond 30-35 ka (~ 100 Gy).

31
32
33 527 The coarse quartz, polymineral pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages largely agree (**Figure 5**)
34
35 528 and within errors are consistent with the expected ages (**Figure 6**).

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37
38 529 Immediately below the S1 paleosol, the coarse quartz, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ yielded
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40 530 ages up to 116 ± 12 ka (262 ± 16 Gy), 130 ± 14 ka (377 ± 19 Gy) and 169 ± 17 ka (490 ± 21 Gy)
41
42 531 respectively. However, it is difficult to interpret these results obtained immediately below S1
43
44 532 paleosol since the doublet samples BAT-1.12A, B, differ by 23% on fine quartz, 10% on
45
46 533 coarse quartz, 38% on pIRIR₂₂₅ and 28% on pIRIR₂₉₀. This causes a difference of 17 ka and
47
48 534 11 ka on fine and coarse quartz and of 36 ka on polymineral fine grains. As the dosimetry
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50 535 data for the doublet samples is consistent, with the exception of ^{210}Pb , the age discrepancies
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52
53 536 seem to originate from the difference between the equivalent doses. More investigations are
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55
56 537 required to explain the different equivalent dose results yielded by doublet samples.
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3 538 For samples taken from deeper units (BAT-1.13A to 1.19A, B), except for fine quartz,
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5
6 539 the natural signal is in the region of laboratory saturation. Interpolation of the natural signal
7
8 540 onto the high curvature region of the dose response curve results in large and asymmetric
9
10 541 uncertainty in the equivalent dose. Consequently, the obtained luminescence ages for samples
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12 542 BAT-1.13A to 1.19A, B have low precision and their reliability is questionable in terms of
13
14
15 543 accuracy, as it is shown in **Section 4.5.2**.

16 17 544 **4.5 Discussion on the accuracy of the reported luminescence ages**

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19 545 In order to identify the factors that control the upper limit of luminescence dating we
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21
22 546 investigate the saturation characteristics of the natural and laboratory signals emitted by both
23
24 547 quartz and polymineral grains.

25 26 548 **4.5.1 Laboratory dose response curves**

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28 549 Laboratory dose response curves up to 5000 Gy have been constructed on sample
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30
31 550 BAT-1.19A collected from below the S3 paleosol (>300 ka according to **Marković et al.,**
32
33 551 **2009**) using 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz as well as polymineral fine grains employing the
34
35 552 pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols (**Figure 7A**). All dose response curves were best fitted with
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37
38 553 a sum of two saturating exponential functions:

$$39
40
41 554 I = I_0 + a(1 - e^{-\frac{D}{D_{01}}}) + c(1 - e^{-\frac{D}{D_{02}}}) \text{ Eq. (1)}$$

42
43 555 where I is the intensity of the signal for a given dose D , I_0 is the intercept, a and b are
44
45 556 the amplitudes of the exponential functions while D_{01} and D_{02} are the doses that characterize
46
47
48 557 the onset of saturation of each exponential function, also named characteristic doses in the
49
50 558 literature. Following the suggestion of **Wintle and Murray (2006)** we consider the saturation
51
52 559 threshold at 85% of the laboratory dose response curve. We assess the closeness to saturation
53
54
55 560 of natural signals by calculating the ratios between the average sensitivity corrected natural
56
57 561 signals ($L_{\text{nat}}/T_{\text{nat}}$) and the corrected luminescence signals measured for the 5000 Gy
58
59 562 regenerative dose (L_x/T_x 5000Gy).

1
2
3 563 The laboratory dose response curve on 63-90 μm quartz saturates much earlier than
4
5 564 fine quartz and polymineral samples and has characteristic saturation doses of $D_{01}=21\pm 28$ Gy
6
7 565 and $D_{02}=153\pm 46$ Gy. The coarse quartz natural signal reaches laboratory saturation. Fine
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9
10 566 quartz on the other hand, yields a laboratory luminescence signal that continues to grow to
11
12 567 doses beyond 5000 Gy and the natural signal is interpolated well below the saturation region
13
14
15 568 of the dose response curve. However, the equivalent dose measured for this sample
16
17 569 underestimates severely the expected equivalent dose (**Table S2**). The characteristic doses for
18
19 570 fine quartz dose response curves are $D_{01}=178\pm 17$ Gy and $D_{02}=1635\pm 164$ Gy. **Timar-Gabor**
20
21 571 **et al. (2012)** also found the natural fine quartz signal of an infinitely old sample from
22
23
24 572 Costinesti LPS (Romania) not to be in saturation. **Timar-Gabor et al. (2017)** determined
25
26 573 similar saturation characteristic doses for worldwide loess and samples of various
27
28 574 sedimentary origins.

30
31 575 It is important to note that pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ laboratory dose response curves
32
33 576 have lower characteristic doses than the fine quartz. We report $D_{01}=142\pm 13$ Gy and
34
35 577 $D_{02}=795\pm 36$ Gy for pIRIR₂₂₅ while for pIRIR₂₉₀ $D_{01}=193\pm 32$ Gy and $D_{02}=764\pm 145$ Gy. The
36
37
38 578 natural pIRIR₂₂₅ signal of sample BAT-1.19A is at $84\pm 0.7\%$ of laboratory saturation while
39
40 579 the natural pIRIR₂₉₀ signal is $105\pm 3\%$ and lies slightly above the light level corresponding to
41
42 580 the 5000 Gy dose (**Figure 7A; Table S7**).

44
45 581 Previous studies document the influence of the magnitude of the test dose on the
46
47 582 pIRIR₂₉₀ laboratory growth curves up to high doses (e.g. **Murray et al., 2014; Yi et al., 2016;**
48
49 583 **Collarosi et al., 2018**). **Figure 7B** shows pIRIR₂₉₀ laboratory dose response curves up to
50
51 584 5000 Gy on sample BAT-1.19A using different test doses: 200 Gy (11% of De), 400 Gy
52
53 585 (22% of De) and 800 Gy (44% of De). The test doses can be expressed as a fraction of light
54
55 586 saturation derived from the growth curve and ratios of 0.37 ± 0.01 , 0.53 ± 0.01 and 0.72 ± 0.01
56
57
58 587 are determined for 200 Gy, 400 Gy and 800 Gy. The growth curves were fitted with a sum of
59
60

588 two saturating exponential functions using **Equation (1)**. The corrected luminescence signals
589 were normalized to the sum of the values of the amplitudes of the exponential functions
590 obtained by fitting (a+c). The saturation parameters (D_{01} ; D_{02}) do not display a significant
591 increase with increased magnitude of test dose (**Table S8**). Based on our finds for Batajnica,
592 we conclude that the dependence of the saturation parameters on the size of the test dose
593 reported for Chinese loess (Yi et al., 2016) or fluvial sediments from South Africa (Collarosi
594 et al., 2018), might not represent a general feature of the pIRIR₂₉₀ laboratory signals.

595 4.5.2 Natural dose response curves

596 To construct natural dose response curves, the average sensitivity corrected natural
597 luminescence signals (L_{nat}/T_{nat}) of the samples listed in **Table S2** were plotted against the
598 expected equivalent doses determined in **Section 4.1**. The natural growth curves are further
599 compared to average laboratory dose response curves in order to assess the reliability of
600 results (**Figure 8**). Fine grained quartz natural and laboratory growth curves overlap until
601 ~150 Gy (**Figure 8A**). This suggests that fine quartz natural signals resulting from doses up
602 to ~150 Gy (~50 ka) could result in reliable ages. For higher natural doses the SAR protocol
603 underestimates the expected fine quartz equivalent doses. Over the entire dose range
604 investigated here, neither the natural nor the laboratory dose response curves reach full
605 saturation. This may be due to the dose range lower than 1200 Gy. This indicates that the fine
606 quartz signals are outside field and laboratory saturation for the entire dose range investigated
607 (**Figure S7** and **Figure 7A**).

608 **Timar-Gabor and Wintle (2013)** reported similar results for fine quartz extracted
609 from the Costinesti LPS in Romania. The natural and laboratory dose response overlap up to
610 ~200 Gy.

611 Coarse-grained quartz natural and laboratory growth curves overlap until ~250 Gy,
612 corresponding to an upper age limit of ~100 ka for Batajnica samples (**Figure 8A**). This

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2
3 613 implies that for natural doses up to 250 Gy (~100 ka), the SAR protocol provides reliable
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5 614 coarse quartz OSL ages. **Figure 9A** and **Figure S7** show that the natural signals emitted by
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7
8 615 coarse quartz samples with measured equivalent doses higher than ~250 Gy (BAT-1.13A to
9
10 616 1.19A) reach field saturation but underestimate the full laboratory saturation by roughly 15
11
12 617 %. Similar results have been reported for “infinitely old” loess samples from Mircea-Voda
13
14 618 LPS in Romania (**Timar-Gabor et al., 2012**) where the laboratory signals overestimate the
15
16 619 natural field saturation by 10-15 %.

19 620 The results obtained on 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz from Batajnica confirm also
20
21 621 the findings of **Chapot et al. (2012)** for 35-63 μm quartz extracted from Chinese loess. They
22
23 622 recommend a maximum limit for OSL dating for an equivalent dose of 150 Gy after
24
25 623 observing the overlap between the natural and laboratory dose response curves.

28 624 The uncorrected pIRIR₂₂₅ natural and laboratory growth curves appear to generally
29
30 625 overlap over the dose range investigated (up to ~ 1200 Gy) (**Figure 8C**). However, the
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32 626 overlap beyond ~ 500 Gy should be interpreted with caution because of the large errors of the
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34 627 data points and their spread along with our observation that the natural signals are in field
35
36 628 saturation (**Figure S7**).

40 629 The natural pIRIR₂₉₀ signals are consistent with the laboratory signals for doses up to
41
42 630 ~ 400 Gy (**Figure 8D**). For higher doses, the natural pIRIR₂₉₀ signals overestimate the
43
44 631 laboratory signals for the Batajnica samples. **Figure 9B** and **Figure S7** show that the
45
46 632 pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ natural signals are in both field and laboratory saturation for samples
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48 633 collected from L2 loess, starting with BAT-1.13A. Similar results have been reported for
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50 634 pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol by **Murray et al. (2014)** on Stari Slankamen LPS, Serbia.

54 635 **4.6 Regional chronostratigraphic correlations**

56 636 Loess records in the southern Middle Danube basin have been investigated intensively
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58 637 for paleoclimate reconstructions (e.g. **Bokhorst et al., 2009; Buggle et al., 2009; Marković**
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3 638 **et al., 2006, 2007, 2014, 2015; Obreht et al., 2019; Stevens et al., 2011**). In particular,
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5 639 trends in environmental magnetic proxies allowed for insights into the regional past long-
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7 640 term climatic and environmental variability, as well as attempting chronostratigraphic
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9 641 correlations among different sections (**Marković et al., 2015**). The magnetic susceptibility
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11 642 records from Batajnica (**Marković et al., 2009**), Stari Slankamen (**Marković et al., 2011**),
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13 643 Rogulić gully and other sections at Titel loess plateau (**Bokhorst et al., 2009; Basarin et al.,**
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15 644 **2014; Perić et al., 2019**), Surduk (**Antoine et al., 2009**) and Crvenka (**Stevens et al., 2011,**
16
17 645 **Marković 2018b**) display similar variability for LGC (**Figure 2**). Nevertheless, despite the
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19 646 available luminescence data for Irig (**Marković et al., 2007**), Surduk (**Fuchs et al., 2008**),
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21 647 Stari Slankamen (**Schmidt et al., 2010; Murray et al., 2014**), Titel (**Perić et al., 2019**),
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23 648 Crvenka (**Stevens et al., 2011**) and Orlovat (**Timar-Gabor et al., 2015**), the coherence in
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25 649 paleoclimate reconstructions among different LPS from southern Middle Danube basin have
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27 650 only been evaluated by astronomically tuning (**Basarin et al., 2014**) and have not been
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29 651 discussed and tested in the frame of absolute luminescence dating.

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35 652 By comparing the existing loess chronologies for individual sites in Serbia with
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37 653 available magnetic susceptibility record (this study and **Antoine et al., 2009; Buggle et al.,**
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39 654 **2009; Perić et al., 2019; Schmidt et al., 2010; Stevens et al., 2011**; Orlovat is not
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41 655 considered due to very strong influence of local conditions and provenance change to
42
43 656 magnetic susceptibility data (**Obreht et al., 2015**)), it can be stated that similarities in
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45 657 magnetic susceptibility variations are also chronologically coherent. Below the Holocene S0
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47 658 soil, intervals with low magnetic susceptibility values are consistently dated to between 20-35
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49 659 ka. In particular, this period is characterised by similarly high dust accumulation rates in the
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51 660 whole region. As an illustrative example, samples at ~2 m depth in all sections with
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53 661 comparable sedimentation rates (Batajnica, Stari Slankamen, Titel and Crvenka) show an age
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3 662 range between 20-30 ka, while samples at ~4.5 m are consistently dated to ~35 ka (**Perić et**
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5 663 **al., 2019; Schmidt et al., 2010; Stevens et al., 2011**, and this study).

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7 664 Beyond this interval (that can be tentatively related to MIS 2), all existing records in
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9 665 the southern Carpathian Basin are dated in considerably lower resolution (with exception of
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11 666 the Titel LPS dated by **Perić et al. (2019)** but with fine quartz ages older than 35 ka
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13 667 considered unreliable), and comparison is more challenging. However, it is evident that the
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15 668 interval 35-40 ka reflects increased variability in magnetic susceptibility values pointing to
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17 669 pedogenesis phases that resulted in weak paleosol formation (i.e., the L1SS1 according to
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19 670 **Marković et al., 2008, 2015**). The following interval is characterized by a decrease in
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21 671 magnetic susceptibility observed at all compared sections, but dated only at Batajnica (this
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23 672 study) and Crvenka (**Stevens et al., 2011**) sections at ~50 ka. **Stevens et al. (2011)** linked this
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25 673 interval to the strong local influence of Heinrich Event 4. Albeit this needs further
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27 674 confirmation, it could also reflect to some degree the impact of the Campanian Ignimbrite/Y-
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29 675 5 ash fall, similarly to what has been observed in the Lower Danube loess records (**Veres et**
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31 676 **al., 2013; Zeeden et al., 2018b; Obrecht et al., 2017**). The next interval comprising loess and
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33 677 very weakly expressed paleosols is characterised by another increase in magnetic
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35 678 susceptibility that likely represents the early MIS 3. However, no direct age estimates are
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37 679 available for this interval and we cannot provide further chronological constrains. Between
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39 680 this layer and the S1 paleosol, a typical loess layer (L1LL2) with low magnetic susceptibility
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41 681 has been tentatively related to MIS 4 by pedostratigraphic correlative techniques (**Marković**
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43 682 **et al., 2015**). For the upper boundary, luminescence ages from Batajnica place L1LL2
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45 683 between ~50 and 58 ka, thus rather within late MIS 4. The L1/S1 transition is placed around
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47 684 ~74 ka and 84 ka based on coarse quartz and pIRIR₂₂₅ ages. Interestingly, in almost all other
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49 685 sections with available age control over L1/S1 (Orlovat, Crvenka, Stari Slankamen), this
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51 686 transition is placed around 60-70 ka. This would suggest that the S1 paleosol as developed in
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3 687 loess might encompass most of MIS 5 (**Marković et al., 2008; 2009; 2015**), and not only the
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5 688 last interglacial optimum (MIS 5e) as previously **Bronger (2003)** proposed. An exception is
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7 689 the Surduk section where the S1/L1 transition has been placed between 75-90 ka (**Fuchs et**
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9 **al., 2008**).

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12 691 Furthermore, establishing secure chronological constrains beyond LGC is very
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14 692 challenging considering limitations in numerical dating, as indicated in this study. However,
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16 693 a more secure regional correlation can be achieved using a tephrostratigraphic approach
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18 694 (**Veres et al., 2013; Insinga et al., 2014; Leicher et al., 2016**). In Southeastern Europe,
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20 695 regional correlation has been widely applied relying on the L2 tephra recorded in many LPS
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22 696 (e.g. **Vandenbergh et al., 2014; Marković et al., 2015; 2018a; Obrecht et al., 2016**).
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24 697 Samples BAT-1.13A, B and BAT-1.14A, B (**Figure 2**) were collected in order to attempt
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26 698 constraining the depositional time of the two visible tephra layers identified within loess unit
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28 699 L2 (equivalent to MIS 6; **Marković et al., 2015**). Whereas glass shards were identified in
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30 700 both tephra layers, (see **Figure S5**) they are altered and microprobe analyses did not allow for
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32 701 diagnostic geochemical fingerprinting. However, as seen in **Figure 2**, the upper L2 tephra is
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34 702 clearly visible in the magnetic susceptibility data, and similar features have been reported in
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36 703 several MIS 6 loess records from the Adriatic coast to the Black sea area (**Laag et al., 2018**).
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38 704 Based on a similar tephra report in Bulgaria, **Antoine et al. (2019)** proposed a correlation
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40 705 with Vico B-ignimbrite dated at 162 ± 8 ka but without reporting any verifiable geochemical
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42 706 data in support. Therefore, it shall be stated that the upper L2 tephra could potentially be the
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44 707 equivalent of one of the tephra layers found in Lake Ohrid (e.g., OH-DP-0617-Vico B at
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46 708 162 ± 6 ka; OH-DP-0624-CF-V5-Pitigliano Tuff at 163 ± 22 ka; **Leicher et al., (2016)**) and in
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48 709 the Fucino basin (e.g., TF-15, TF-16, TF-17; **Giaccio et al., 2017**) and dated to 150-160 ka.
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50 710 The Mediterranean Sea tephra data also document several major tephra layers between 140-
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52 711 170 ka (**Insinga et al., 2014**). Moreover, as seen also at Batajnica, at least two tephra layers
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3 712 are preserved regionally within the L2 loess; this highlights the risk in deriving ages without
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5 713 proper geochemical control, especially when at the limit of reliable luminescence dating
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8 714 (**Table 1**).

9 10 715 **5. Conclusions**

11
12 716 Luminescence dating of 63-90 μm quartz and 4-11 μm polymineral grains using the
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14 717 pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol provided age estimates for the LGC at Batajnica that generally agree with
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16 718 the previously established correlative chronological scheme proposed by **Marković et al.**
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18 719 (**2009**). The 63-90 μm quartz ages are reliable up to 100 ka before exhibiting field and
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20 720 laboratory saturation. The 4-11 μm quartz yields reliable ages only for MIS 2 loess samples
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22 721 and increasingly underestimates the true depositional time for older samples. The pIRIR₂₂₅
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24 722 and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols applied on 4-11 μm polymineral grains provide reliable ages over the
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26 723 LGC, beyond which they are in field and laboratory saturation. Interpretation of the pIRIR₂₂₅
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28 724 and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages obtained immediately below the Last Interglacial paleosol is hampered by
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30 725 different results yielded by doublet samples.

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33 726 The upper limit of the luminescence dating methods at Batajnica is imposed by
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35 727 saturation of the natural signals starting with samples collected from L2 loess (BAT-1.13A-
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37 728 1.19A, B).

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40 729 The observed similarities in pacing of magnetic susceptibility records in the majority
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42 730 of sites in Northern Serbia are chronologically coherent with the Batajnica section and master
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44 731 global records. This allowed us to construct natural dose response curves. The comparison
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46 732 between the natural and laboratory dose response curves predicts the dose range over which
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48 733 reliable luminescence ages are obtained for each signal investigated. For 4-11 μm and 63-90
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50 734 μm quartz, the natural and laboratory dose response curves overlap until ~ 150 Gy and ~ 250
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52 735 Gy, respectively, while for the pIRIR₂₂₅ an apparent overlap of the natural growth curve up to
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54 736 at least 500 Gy. The pIRIR₂₉₀ natural and laboratory growth curves are consistent with the
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3 737 laboratory dose response curve up to doses of 400 Gy beyond which the natural signals
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5 738 overestimate the laboratory signals.
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9
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Table 1. Summary of the OSL, pIRIR290 and pIRIR225 ages considering the residual dose estimated based on modern analogue sample. With * is indicated the set of polymineral ages considering the residual dose measured after laboratory bleaching. The age uncertainties were determined following **Aitken and Allred (1972)**. The uncertainties associated with the luminescence and dosimetry data are random; the uncertainties mentioned with the optical ages are the overall uncertainties. The systematic errors taken into account include: 2% beta source calibration, 3% conversion factors, 5% attenuation and etching factors, 3% gamma spectrometer calibration, 15% cosmic radiation, 25% water content. All uncertainties represent 1σ. Specific activities were measured on well detector by gamma spectrometry and the ages were determined considering 15% water content; beta attenuation and etching factors used for 63-90 μm quartz were 0.94±0.05 (**Mejdahl, 1979**); adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04±0.02 for 4-11 μm quartz and 0.08±0.02 for polymineral 4-11 μm fine grains, respectively (**Rees-Jones, 1995**). The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations for coarse grains as well as the contribution from alpha radiations in the case of fine grains. The contribution of cosmic radiation was taken into account and calculated accordingly to **Prescott and Hutton (1994)**. For coarse quartz grains an internal dose rate of 0.01±0.002 Gy/ka was considered (**Vandenbergh et al., 2008**). The equivalent doses given in italics are calculated by interpolating natural signals onto the saturation region of the dose response curve.

Sample code	Stratigraphic units	Depth (cm)	ED (Gy)				Total random error (%)				Total systematic error (%)				Total dose rate (Gy/ka)				Age (ka)				Age (ka)*		
			4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	4-11 μm quartz	63-90 μm quartz	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	pIRIR ₂₉₀ pfg	pIRIR ₂₂₅ pfg	
BAT 1.0	S0/L1	87	31 ± 1	28 ± 1	36 ± 9	37 ± 6	4.3	4.6	25.2	16.5	8.8	6.7	8.4	8.4	2.9±0.08	2.4±0.07	3.2±0.09	3.2±0.09	11±1	12±1	11±3	12±2	22±2	19±2	
BAT 1.1	L1	103	37 ± 1	40 ± 2	43 ± 9	45 ± 6	4.1	5.9	21.2	13.7	8.7	6.8	8.3	8.3	2.9±0.09	2.4±0.07	3.3±0.11	3.3±0.11	13±1	17±2	13±3	14±2	24±2	22±2	
BAT 1.7		214	74 ± 1	91 ± 6	89 ± 10	91 ± 7	2.7	7.0	11.5	8.0	9.0	6.8	8.6	8.6	3.1±0.07	2.6±0.06	3.6±0.08	3.6±0.08	24±2	35±3	26±4	26±3	36±4	33±3	
BAT 1.8		423	108 ± 1	110 ± 6	121 ± 9	105 ± 11	2.6	6.0	7.8	10.7	9.2	6.9	8.8	8.8	3.5±0.08	2.9±0.07	4.0±0.10	4.0±0.10	31±3	38±3	31±4	27±4	39±4	33±4	
BAT 1.9		641	145 ± 3	116 ± 6	185 ± 18	162 ± 10	4.7	6.6	10.7	7.6	8.8	6.9	8.5	8.5	2.9±0.12	2.4±0.10	3.2±0.12	3.2±0.12	51±5	48±5	57±8	50±6	69±8	58±6	
BAT 1.10		821	176 ± 2	168 ± 7	217 ± 16	189 ± 10	3.2	5.1	8.0	6.1	8.6	7.0	8.3	8.3	2.8±0.08	2.4±0.07	3.1±0.10	3.1±0.10	62±6	70±6	69±8	60±7	80±8	68±7	
BAT 1.11		S1/L1	953	217 ± 4	211 ± 8	328 ± 14	292 ± 23	3.1	4.6	5.0	8.3	8.8	7.0	8.4	8.4	3.4±0.09	2.9±0.07	3.8±0.10	3.8±0.10	64±6	74±6	87±9	77±9	96±9	84±9
BAT 1.12 A		L2/S1	1200	237 ± 3	224 ± 12	490 ± 21	377 ± 19	3.3	6.2	5.3	5.9	9.3	7.0	8.9	8.9	2.6±0.08	2.1±0.06	2.9±0.09	2.9±0.09	93±9	105±10	169±17	130±14	181±18	138±14
BAT 1.12 B			1200	206 ± 4	262 ± 16	408 ± 15	290 ± 13	4.3	7.2	5.3	5.9	9.5	6.9	9.0	9.0	2.7±0.10	2.3±0.08	3.1±0.12	3.1±0.12	76±8	116±12	132±14	94±11	143±15	102±11
BAT 1.13 A		L2	1300	275 ± 8	<i>307 ± 33</i>	<i>743 ± 42</i>	<i>572 ± 17</i>	4.5	11.2	6.6	4.6	8.9	7.0	8.6	8.6	2.5±0.09	2.1±0.07	2.9±0.09	2.9±0.09	108±11	<i>144±19</i>	<i>260±28</i>	<i>200±20</i>	<i>273±29</i>	<i>209±20</i>
BAT 1.13 B			1300	345 ± 9	<i>357 ± 46</i>	<i>745 ± 41</i>	<i>734 ± 33</i>	4.2	13.3	6.4	5.6	8.7	7.0	8.3	8.3	2.7±0.09	2.3±0.07	3.0±0.10	3.0±0.10	130±13	<i>159±24</i>	<i>252±27</i>	<i>249±25</i>	<i>264±27</i>	<i>257±26</i>
BAT 1.14 A	1450		334 ± 7	<i>280 ± 28</i>	<i>762 ± 63</i>	<i>542 ± 17</i>	3.6	10.4	8.8	4.3	9.1	7.0	8.7	8.7	2.6±0.08	2.2±0.06	2.9±0.09	2.9±0.09	129±13	<i>129±16</i>	<i>261±32</i>	<i>185±18</i>	<i>272±33</i>	<i>194±19</i>	
BAT 1.14 B	1450		359 ± 11	<i>291 ± 16</i>	<i>843 ± 68</i>	<i>661 ± 42</i>	4.4	6.3	8.7	7.1	9.2	7.0	8.8	8.8	2.7±0.09	2.2±0.07	3.0±0.09	3.0±0.09	134±14	<i>131±12</i>	<i>279±35</i>	<i>219±25</i>	<i>291±35</i>	<i>227±25</i>	
BAT 1.16	S2/L2	1650	348 ± 6	<i>366 ± 53</i>	<i>1137 ± 129</i>	<i>690 ± 28</i>	3.5	14.8	11.7	5.0	9.2	7.0	8.7	8.7	2.9±0.09	2.4±0.07	3.2±0.10	3.2±0.10	122±12	<i>153±25</i>	<i>353±52</i>	<i>214±22</i>	<i>363±52</i>	<i>221±22</i>	
BAT 1.17	L3/S2	1900	383 ± 12	<i>333 ± 31</i>	<i>1119 ± 126</i>	<i>629 ± 24</i>	4.2	9.7	11.6	4.7	8.9	7.1	8.5	8.5	2.7±0.07	2.3±0.06	3.0±0.09	3.0±0.09	143±14	<i>147±18</i>	<i>373±54</i>	<i>210±20</i>	<i>385±54</i>	<i>217±21</i>	
BAT 1.18		1900	386 ± 10	<i>377 ± 27</i>	<i>1012 ± 107</i>	<i>532 ± 51</i>	3.6	7.6	10.9	9.9	8.9	7.1	8.5	8.5	2.7±0.06	2.3±0.05	3.0±0.08	3.0±0.08	145±14	<i>168±17</i>	<i>339±47</i>	<i>178±23</i>	<i>351±47</i>	<i>186±24</i>	
BAT 1.19 A	L4/S3	2400	486 ± 5	<i>345 ± 23</i>		<i>1178 ± 66</i>	2.7	7.2		6.1	9.3	7.1		8.9	3.2±0.08	2.7±0.07		3.4±0.09	150±15	<i>128±13</i>		<i>322±35</i>		<i>328±35</i>	
BAT 1.19 B		2400	475 ± 7	<i>414 ± 37</i>		<i>1244 ± 62</i>	3.5	9.5		5.9	9.1	7.2		8.7	3.1±0.10	2.6±0.08		3.2±0.11	153±15	<i>159±19</i>		<i>356±38</i>		<i>362±38</i>	

Figure 1. The study area integrated in the map of loess distribution after **Haase et al. (2007)**. SRTM data provided by U.S. Geological Survey. The star represents the investigated loess site, while loess sites mentioned in this paper are given with solid circles (Mircea-Voda, Romania (**Timar-Gabor et al., 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012**); Stari Slankamen, Serbia (**Murray et al., 2014**); Crvenka, Serbia (**Stevens et al., 2011**); Stratzing, Austria (**Thiel et al., 2011a**)).

Figure 2. Stratigraphy and magnetic susceptibility of the Batajnica site (Marković et al., 2009) and its correlation to astronomically tuned magnetic susceptibility record from the Titel/Stari Slankamen composite record (Basarin et al., 2014) and benthic oxygen isotope stack (Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005). Paleosols are marked from S0 to S5. Dashed lines indicate loess-paleosol transitions at the Batajnica site and corresponding ages at the Titel/Stari Slankamen composite record and benthic oxygen isotope stack. On the stratigraphic column, the two tephra layers identified in L2 loess layer are represented with dashed lines.

Figure 3. Dose recovery test results for (A) fine (open squares) and coarse (open circles) quartz, (B) polymineral fine grains on pIRIR₂₉₀ (open diamonds) and pIRIR₂₂₅ (open triangles). The given irradiation doses were chosen to match the equivalent dose of each sample. The solid line indicates the ideal 1:1 dose recovery ratio while the dash lines bracket a 10% variation from unity.

Figure 4. Dependence of measured pIRIR₂₉₀ equivalent dose on the size of test dose for samples **BAT-1.9** (open symbols), **BAT-1.12A** (filled symbols). The expected equivalent doses for sample **BAT-1.12A**, taken from **Table S2**, are highlighted with grey. Solid lines are used to indicate the expected values while error ranges are given by dashed lines.

Figure 5. Quartz OSL and polymineral pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ ages for the uppermost loess-paleosol alternation in Batajnica site. Please note the doublet samples collected at 12 m depth: open symbols indicate sample BAT-1.12A while filled symbols represent sample BAT-1.12B.

Figure 6. Luminescence ages plotted against expected ages for samples BAT-1.0, BAT-1.11, BAT-1.12A and BAT-1.12B (filled symbols). The expected ages are derived from correlation of loess-paleosol boundaries with benthic isotope stack (see **Figure 2** and **Table S2**).

A)

B)

Figure 7 (A) Laboratory dose response curves constructed for 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz, 4-11 μm polymineral grains measured with pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols on sample BAT-1.19A (> 300 ka). All growth curves were fitted with a sum of two saturating exponential functions. Each datapoint represents an average of three measurements. Horizontal lines indicate the average natural sensitivity corrected luminescence signals ($L_{\text{nat}}/T_{\text{nat}}$). The average $L_{\text{nat}}/T_{\text{nat}}$ obtained on all aliquots measured, including De measurements, is interpolated on the growth curve. The percentage indicated for each interpolation represents the ratio between the $L_{\text{nat}}/T_{\text{nat}}$ and the L_x/T_x measured for the 5000 Gy regenerative dose.

(B) pIRIR₂₉₀ laboratory dose response curves constructed on sample BAT-1.19A with different test doses: 17 Gy (0.9%·De), 200 Gy (11%·De), 400 Gy (22%·De) and 800 Gy (44%·De). Three aliquots have been measured for each test dose. All growth curves were fitted with a sum of two saturating exponential functions ($I=I_0+a\cdot(1-\exp(-D/D_{01}))+c\cdot(1-\exp(-D/D_{02}))$). The corrected luminescence signals have been normalized to the sum of the amplitude of the exponential functions obtained by fitting ($a+c$).

A)

B)

C)

D)

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3 **Figure 8.** Average of natural sensitivity corrected luminescence signals emitted by (A) 4-11 μm and (B) 63-90 μm quartz, 4-11 μm polymineral
4 grains measured with (C) pIRIR₂₂₅ and (D) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols, plotted as function of expected equivalent doses for the samples collected from
5 the loess/paleosols boundaries (BAT-1.0, BAT-1.11, BAT-1.12A, BAT-1.12B, BAT-1.16, BAT-1.17, BAT-1.19A). The expected equivalent
6 doses are derived from the magnetic susceptibility data correlated to the benthic oxygen stack (Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005). The average
7 laboratory dose response is presented for comparison. Data are fitted by a sum of two saturating exponential functions. Please note the small
8 vertical uncertainties on the corrected natural light levels.
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Figure 9. Ratios of the sensitivity corrected natural signals to the sensitivity corrected luminescence signals induced by 5000 Gy dose calculated for (A) quartz and (B) polymineral fine grains samples collected from below the last interglacial paleosol. The threshold of saturation is given by dashed lines and it is set at 0.85. Please note that the laboratory signal emitted by fine quartz continues to grow to doses higher than 5000 Gy (see **Figure 7A**).

Supplementary material- Testing polymineral post-IR IRSL and quartz SAR-OSL protocols on Middle to Late Pleistocene loess at Batajnica, Serbia

Table S1. Flowchart of the SAR-OSL on quartz (Murray and Wintle, 2000, 2003), pIRIR₂₉₀(Thiel et al., 2011a; Buylaert et al., 2011b, 2012) and pIRIR₂₂₅(Buylaert et al., 2009; Wacha and Frechen, 2011; Vasiliniuc et al., 2012) protocols applied in this study.(*). Unless otherwise stated.

step	a. SAR protocol	b. pIRIR ₂₉₀	c. pIRIR ₂₂₅
1	Dose	Dose	Dose
2	Preheat (125 C; 10s)	Preheat (320 C; 60s)	Preheat (250 C; 60s)
3	Blue OSL (125 C; 40s)	IRSL (50 C; 200s)	IRSL (50 C; 200s)
4	Test dose (17Gy)*	IRSL (290 C; 200s)	IRSL (225 C; 200s)
5	Cutheat (180 C)	Test dose (17Gy)*	Test dose (17Gy)*
6	Blue OSL (125 C; 40s)	Preheat (320 C; 60s)	Preheat (250 C; 60s)
7	Blue OSL (280 C; 40s)	IRSL (50 C; 200s)	IRSL (50 C; 200s)
8		IRSL (290 C; 200s)	IRSL (225 C; 200s)
9		IRSL (325 C; 100s)	IRSL (290 C; 100s)

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Table S2. Information on the samples used for the construction of the natural dose response curves. The expected ages are from correlation of the paleosol/loess boundaries with benthic isotope stack (**Lisiecki and Raymo, 2005**). The expected equivalent dose (De) for each sample was calculated by multiplying the annual dose rate by the expected age.

Sample code	Sampling information	Boundary age (ka)	Grain size (μm)	Annual dose (Gy/ka)	Expected De (Gy)
BAT 1.0	L1/S0	11.5 \pm 1	4-11 quartz	2.9 \pm 0.3	33 \pm 4
			63-90 quartz	2.4 \pm 0.2	28 \pm 3
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.2 \pm 0.3	37 \pm 5
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.2 \pm 0.3	37 \pm 5
BAT 1.11	S1/L1	80 \pm 8	4-11 quartz	3.4 \pm 0.3	270 \pm 37
			63-90 quartz	2.9 \pm 0.2	228 \pm 28
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.8 \pm 0.3	302 \pm 40
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.8 \pm 0.3	302 \pm 40
BAT 1.12A	L2/S1	130 \pm 13	4-11 quartz	2.6 \pm 0.3	332 \pm 46
			63-90 quartz	2.1 \pm 0.2	277 \pm 35
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	2.9 \pm 0.3	377 \pm 52
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	2.9 \pm 0.3	377 \pm 52
BAT 1.12B	L2/S1	130 \pm 13	4-11 quartz	2.7 \pm 0.3	354 \pm 51
			63-90 quartz	2.3 \pm 0.2	293 \pm 37
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.1 \pm 0.3	403 \pm 56
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.1 \pm 0.3	403 \pm 56
BAT 1.16	S2/L2	191 \pm 19	4-11 quartz	2.9 \pm 0.3	546 \pm 76
			63-90 quartz	2.4 \pm 0.2	456 \pm 57
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.2 \pm 0.3	617 \pm 84
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.2 \pm 0.3	617 \pm 84
BAT 1.17	L3/S2	228 \pm 23	4-11 quartz	2.7 \pm 0.2	611 \pm 83
			63-90 quartz	2.3 \pm 0.2	515 \pm 65
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.0 \pm 0.3	684 \pm 92
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.0 \pm 0.3	684 \pm 92
BAT 1.19A	Lower boundary S3	322 \pm 32	4-11 quartz	3.2 \pm 0.3	1043 \pm 145
			63-90 quartz	2.7 \pm 0.2	869 \pm 109
			pIRIR ₂₉₀	3.7 \pm 0.3	1179 \pm 160
			pIRIR ₂₂₅	3.7 \pm 0.3	1179 \pm 160

Supplementary material- Testing polymineral post-IR IRSL and quartz SAR-OSL protocols on Middle to Late Pleistocene loess at Batajnica, Serbia

Table S3. Summary of dosimetry data. The uncertainties associated with the annual doses are random. Specific activities were measured on well detector by gamma spectrometry and the ages were determined considering 15% water content; beta attenuation and etching factors used for 63-90 μm quartz were 0.94 ± 0.05 (Mejdahl, 1979); adopted alpha efficiency factor was 0.04 ± 0.02 for 4-11 μm quartz and 0.08 ± 0.02 for polymineral 4-11 μm fine grains, respectively (Rees-Jones, 1995). The total dose rate consists of the contribution from the beta and gamma radiations for coarse grains as well as the contribution from alpha radiations in the case of fine grains. The contribution of cosmic radiation was taken into account and calculated accordingly to Prescott and Hutton (1994). For coarse quartz grains an internal dose rate of 0.01 ± 0.002 Gy/ka was considered (Vandenberghe et al., 2008).

Sample code	Radionuclide activities				Annual doses			
	^{210}Pb	^{232}Th	^{226}Ra	^{40}K	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	pIRIR ₂₉₀	pIRIR ₂₂₅
BAT 1.0	16 \pm 4	41.3 \pm 1.2	40.4 \pm 0.2	422 \pm 16	2.9 \pm 0.08	2.4 \pm 0.07	3.2 \pm 0.09	3.2 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.1	21 \pm 4	36.9 \pm 1.5	38.8 \pm 1.7	440 \pm 16	2.9 \pm 0.09	2.4 \pm 0.07	3.3 \pm 0.11	3.3 \pm 0.11
BAT 1.7	24 \pm 4	39.9 \pm 0.3	47.8 \pm 0.4	463 \pm 14	3.1 \pm 0.07	2.6 \pm 0.06	3.6 \pm 0.08	3.6 \pm 0.08
BAT 1.8	27 \pm 4	49.7 \pm 0.3	53.8 \pm 1.5	510 \pm 17	3.5 \pm 0.08	2.9 \pm 0.07	4.0 \pm 0.10	4.0 \pm 0.10
BAT 1.9	15 \pm 5	41.0 \pm 3.2	40.5 \pm 1.1	468 \pm 19	2.9 \pm 0.12	2.4 \pm 0.10	3.2 \pm 0.12	3.2 \pm 0.12
BAT 1.10	14 \pm 4	38.1 \pm 0.7	35.9 \pm 1.1	497 \pm 17	2.8 \pm 0.08	2.4 \pm 0.07	3.1 \pm 0.10	3.1 \pm 0.10
BAT 1.11	24 \pm 4	43.5 \pm 0.4	43.6 \pm 0.5	568 \pm 19	3.4 \pm 0.09	2.9 \pm 0.07	3.8 \pm 0.10	3.8 \pm 0.10
BAT 1.12A	22 \pm 4	36.5 \pm 0.4	38.1 \pm 1.2	373 \pm 14	2.6 \pm 0.08	2.1 \pm 0.06	2.9 \pm 0.09	2.9 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.12B	30 \pm 6	38.0 \pm 0.2	38.7 \pm 0.6	370 \pm 17	2.7 \pm 0.10	2.3 \pm 0.08	3.1 \pm 0.12	3.1 \pm 0.12
BAT 1.13A	15 \pm 4	35.7 \pm 1.7	35.5 \pm 0.4	418 \pm 15	2.5 \pm 0.09	2.1 \pm 0.07	2.9 \pm 0.09	2.9 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.13B	13 \pm 4	35.4 \pm 0.6	35.4 \pm 0.6	467 \pm 17	2.7 \pm 0.09	2.3 \pm 0.07	3.0 \pm 0.10	3.0 \pm 0.10
BAT 1.14A	16 \pm 4	37.7 \pm 0.6	38.8 \pm 0.6	409 \pm 16	2.6 \pm 0.08	2.2 \pm 0.06	2.9 \pm 0.09	2.9 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.14B	14 \pm 4	42.4 \pm 1.7	38.4 \pm 0.9	415 \pm 17	2.7 \pm 0.09	2.2 \pm 0.07	3.0 \pm 0.09	3.0 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.16	25 \pm 4	39.7 \pm 0.7	36.9 \pm 0.7	441 \pm 17	2.9 \pm 0.09	2.4 \pm 0.07	3.2 \pm 0.10	3.2 \pm 0.10
BAT 1.17	12 \pm 4	38.9 \pm 0.4	36.6 \pm 1.2	463 \pm 14	2.7 \pm 0.07	2.3 \pm 0.06	3.0 \pm 0.09	3.0 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.18	13 \pm 3	38.4 \pm 0.6	36.3 \pm 0.7	459 \pm 13	2.7 \pm 0.06	2.3 \pm 0.05	3.0 \pm 0.08	3.0 \pm 0.08
BAT 1.19A	20 \pm 4	54.6 \pm 1.5	38.0 \pm 1.5	496 \pm 15	3.2 \pm 0.08	2.7 \pm 0.07		3.4 \pm 0.09
BAT 1.19B	20 \pm 5	50.2 \pm 0.8	32.0 \pm 0.7	496 \pm 17	3.1 \pm 0.10	2.6 \pm 0.08		3.2 \pm 0.11

Supplementary material- Testing polymineral post-IR IRSL and quartz SAR-OSL protocols on Middle to Late Pleistocene loess at Batajnica, Serbia

Table S4. The measured equivalent doses along with the performance parameters of the SAR-OSL protocol as well as for pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ for each quartz grain-size and polymineral fine grains. The number of aliquots (*n*) averaged for equivalent dose calculation is also given. Quoted errors represent 1σ. The equivalent doses given in italics are calculated by interpolating natural signals onto the saturation region of the dose response curve.

Sample code	Depth	ED (Gy)				Recycling				IR depletion		Recuperation (%)			
		4-11 μm	63-90 μm	pIRIR ₂₉₀	pIRIR ₂₂₅	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	pIRIR ₂₉₀	pIRIR ₂₂₅	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	4-11 μm	63-90 μm	pIRIR ₂₉₀	pIRIR ₂₂₅
BAT 1.0	87	31 ± 1 (n=19)	28 ± 1 (n=18)	80 ± 8 (n=6)	63 ± 1 (n=6)	1.01 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.29	0.15 ± 0.03	1.66 ± 0.11	2.18 ± 0.09
BAT 1.1	103	37 ± 1 (n=12)	40 ± 2 (n=20)	87 ± 3 (n=5)	71 ± 1 (n=6)	1.07 ± 0.06	0.98 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.02	1.00 ± 0.02	1.01 ± 0.04	0.98 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.25	0.17 ± 0.04	2.00 ± 0.11	2.06 ± 0.12
BAT 1.7	214	74 ± 1 (n=15)	91 ± 6 (n=11)	133 ± 6 (n=6)	117 ± 4 (n=5)	0.99 ± 0.02	0.99 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.02	1.03 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.04	0.10 ± 0.12	1.07 ± 0.06	1.51 ± 0.12
BAT 1.8	423	108 ± 1 (n=13)	110 ± 6 (n=14)	165 ± 4 (n=6)	131 ± 9 (n=5)	0.95 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.04	1.29 ± 0.05	1.28 ± 0.09
BAT 1.9	641	145 ± 3 (n=15)	116 ± 6 (n=11)	230 ± 16 (n=6)	188 ± 8 (n=6)	0.97 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.02	0.08 ± 0.02	0.60 ± 0.28	0.77 ± 0.28	0.83 ± 0.11
BAT 1.10	821	176 ± 2 (n=10)	168 ± 7 (n=10)	261 ± 14 (n=6)	215 ± 8 (n=6)	0.96 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.04	0.99 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.02	0.03 ± 0.01	0.02 ± 0.06	0.95 ± 0.21	0.98 ± 0.08
BAT 1.11	953	217 ± 4 (n=13)	211 ± 8 (n=12)	373 ± 12 (n=11)	318 ± 22 (n=6)	0.96 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.02	1.30 ± 0.12	0.77 ± 0.01
BAT 1.12 A	1200	237 ± 3 (n=11)	224 ± 12 (n=11)	534 ± 19 (n=10)	403 ± 18 (n=5)	0.94 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.03	0.97 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.04 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.06	0.92 ± 0.06
BAT 1.12 B	1200	206 ± 4 (n=11)	262 ± 16 (n=13)	452 ± 12 (n=10)	316 ± 11 (n=6)	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.95 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.05 ± 0.01	0.10 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.04	1.05 ± 0.08
BAT 1.13 A	1300	275 ± 8 (n=12)	<i>307 ± 33 (n=11)</i>	<i>787 ± 41 (n=9)</i>	<i>598 ± 16 (n=6)</i>	0.99 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.02	0.92 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.07 ± 0.03	0.29 ± 0.11	0.97 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.06
BAT 1.13 B	1300	345 ± 9 (n=13)	<i>357 ± 46 (n=14)</i>	<i>789 ± 40 (n=6)</i>	<i>760 ± 33 (n=6)</i>	0.98 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.89 ± 0.03	0.94 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01	0.97 ± 0.02	0.06 ± 0.01	0.00 ± 0.02	0.84 ± 0.06	0.97 ± 0.07
BAT 1.14 A	1450	334 ± 7 (n=10)	<i>280 ± 28 (n=13)</i>	<i>806 ± 63 (n=8)</i>	<i>568 ± 16 (n=6)</i>	0.96 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.02	0.90 ± 0.01	0.98 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.92 ± 0.01	0.08 ± 0.01	0.26 ± 0.12	0.98 ± 0.05	0.91 ± 0.03
BAT 1.14 B	1450	359 ± 11 (n=14)	<i>291 ± 16 (n=10)</i>	<i>887 ± 68 (n=7)</i>	<i>687 ± 41 (n=6)</i>	0.96 ± 0.01	0.99 ± 0.02	0.88 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.02	0.94 ± 0.01	1.01 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.01	0.15 ± 0.15	1.06 ± 0.03	0.93 ± 0.05
BAT 1.16	1650	348 ± 6 (n=10)	<i>366 ± 53 (n=10)</i>	<i>1181 ± 129 (n=9)</i>	<i>716 ± 27 (n=10)</i>	0.95 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.03	0.92 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.00	0.89 ± 0.01	0.07 ± 0.01	0.24 ± 0.06	0.91 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.04
BAT 1.17	1900	383 ± 12 (n=12)	<i>333 ± 31 (n=12)</i>	<i>1163 ± 126 (n=6)</i>	<i>655 ± 24 (n=8)</i>	0.95 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.03	0.99 ± 0.02	0.96 ± 0.01	0.94 ± 0.02	0.17 ± 0.06	0.66 ± 0.26	1.02 ± 0.05	0.92 ± 0.07
BAT 1.18	1900	386 ± 10 (n=13)	<i>377 ± 27 (n=10)</i>	<i>1056 ± 107 (n=6)</i>	<i>558 ± 51 (n=6)</i>	0.97 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.02	1.0 ± 0.04	1.02 ± 0.02	0.97 ± 0.01	0.93 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.02	0.74 ± 0.11	0.89 ± 0.03	0.13 ± 0.00
BAT 1.19 A	2400	486 ± 5 (n=11)	<i>345 ± 23 (n=13)</i>		<i>1204 ± 66 (n=8)</i>	0.97 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01		0.95 ± 0.02	0.95 ± 0.01	0.90 ± 0.01	0.17 ± 0.05	1.57 ± 0.28		0.80 ± 0.04
BAT 1.19 B	2400	475 ± 7 (n=11)	<i>414 ± 37 (n=14)</i>		<i>1270 ± 62 (n=7)</i>	0.97 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01		0.94 ± 0.01	0.96 ± 0.01	0.91 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01	0.36 ± 0.05		0.80 ± 0.03

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Table S5. The measured residual doses along with the performance parameters of the pIRIR₂₉₀ procedure for fine (4-11 μm) polymineral grains of the ten samples analysed. Three or four aliquots from each sample were exposed to lamp for one month and then the residual dose was measured in the usual manner (same measurement protocol as for equivalent dose determination described in main text **Section 4.3**). The aliquots with poor recycling ratio (exceeding 10% from unity) were rejected. * indicate the equivalent doses measured for the samples with natural signal close to saturation.

Sample code	Uncorrected De pIRIR ₂₉₀ (Gy)	Residual De pIRIR ₂₉₀ (Gy)	Recycling	Recuperation (%)
BAT 1.7	133±6 (n=6/6)	5.7±0.5 (n=4/4)	1.01±0.04	9.1±2.0
BAT 1.8	165±4 (n=6/6)	5.6±1.1 (n=4/4)	1.00±0.02	8.2±0.9
BAT 1.9	230±16 (n=6/6)	7.5±1.2 (n=3/4)	0.96±0.03	9.8±1.6
BAT 1.10	261±14 (n=6/6)	10.5±0.7 (n=3/3)	1.02±0.04	5.6±1.6
BAT 1.11	373±12 (n=11/11)	9.1±1.2 (n=2/3)	1.02±0.07	6.1±1.3
BAT 1.12 A	534±19 (n=10/12)	8.3±3.2 (n=2/3)	0.09±0.01	2.8±0.2
BAT 1.12 B	452±12 (n=10/12)	6.3±0.9 (n=2/3)	0.92±0.01	10.3±1.2
BAT 1.13 A	787±41 (n=9/11)*	12.3±0.8 (n=3/3)	0.90±0.02	5.4±1.4
BAT 1.13 B	789±40 (n=6/6)*	12.9±1.3 (n=3/3)	0.96±0.02	6.9±1.6
BAT 1.14 A	806±63 (n=8/9)*	11.1±1.6 (n=3/3)	0.91±0.01	8.6±0.9

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Table S6. The measured residual doses along with the performance parameters of the pIRIR₂₂₅ procedure for fine (4-11 μm) polymineral grains of the nine samples analyzed. Four or five aliquots from each sample were exposed to lamp for one month and then the residual dose was measured in the usual manner (same measurement protocol as for equivalent dose determination described in main text **Section 4.3**). * indicate the equivalent doses measured for the samples with natural signal close to saturation.

Sample code	Uncorrected De pIRIR ₂₂₅ (Gy)	Residual De pIRIR ₂₂₅ (Gy)	Recycling	Recuperation (%)
BAT 1.10	215±8 (n=6/6)	0.6±0.1 (n=5/5)	0.76±0.06	41±14
BAT 1.11	318±22 (n=6/6)	1.3±0.2 (n=5/5)	0.91±0.09	24±5
BAT 1.12B	316±11 (n=6/6)	1.6±0.2 (n=4/4)	0.75±0.07	38±7
BAT 1.14B	<i>687±41 (n=6/6)*</i>	1.9±0.4 (n=4/4)	0.96±0.03	28±3
BAT 1.16	<i>716±27 (n=10/10)*</i>	1.8±0.7 (n=4/4)	0.97±0.02	36±4
BAT 1.17	<i>655±24 (n=8/9)*</i>	2.5±0.3 (n=4/4)	1.01±0.05	42±2
BAT 1.18	<i>558±51 (n=6/6)*</i>	2.5±0.4 (n=4/4)	0.95±0.03	36±6
BAT 1.19A	<i>1204±66 (n=8/8)*</i>	2.6±0.5 (n=4/4)	1.02±0.03	41±5
BAT 1.19B	<i>1270±62 (n=7/7)*</i>	3.2±0.2 (n=4/4)	0.94±0.02	37±2

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Table S7. g-values measured on polymineral fine grains using pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ protocols as well as on fine and coarse quartz using SAR-OSL protocol.

Sample code	protocol	aliq	g value (%)	Average g-value (%)
BAT 1.11 4-11 μm polymineral	pIRIR ₂₉₀	1	0.01 \pm 1.12	1.3 \pm 0.6
		2	1.77 \pm 1.02	
		3	2.69 \pm 1.08	
		4	0.64 \pm 1.01	
BAT 1.11 4-11 μm polymineral	pIRIR ₂₂₅	1	-0.82 \pm -0.71	0.5 \pm 0.5
		2	1.14 \pm 0.74	
		3	1.18 \pm 0.74	
		4	0.54 \pm 0.76	
BAT 1.19A 4-11 μm polymineral	pIRIR ₂₂₅	1	2.17 \pm 1.59	3.2 \pm 0.4
		2	2.86 \pm 1.71	
		3	3.48 \pm 1.67	
		4	4.23 \pm 1.72	
BAT 1.11 4-11 μm quartz	SAR-OSL	1	3.11 \pm 1.03	2.5 \pm 0.4
		2	2.71 \pm 0.88	
		3	1.65 \pm 1.08	
BAT 1.11 63-90 μm quartz	SAR-OSL	1	4.28 \pm 0.86	2.9 \pm 0.6
		2	3.24 \pm 0.75	
		3	1.34 \pm 0.72	
		4	2.80 \pm 0.08	

Table S8. Maximum corrected luminescence signals in the SAR-OSL and pIRIR protocols used and natural corrected luminescence signals for the sample BAT-1.19A. The last column presents the ratio of the natural signal to signal obtained for a given dose of 5000Gy, used as an indication of the closeness of the signal to saturation

Sample code	Grain size	L_n/T_n average	$L_x/T_{x5000\text{ Gy}}$	$(L_n/T_n)/(L_x/T_x 5000\text{Gy})$
BAT-1.19A	4-11 μm quartz	9.6 \pm 0.1 n=11	17.2 \pm 0.4 n=3	0.56 \pm 0.01
	63-90 μm quartz	5.2 \pm 0.2 n=13	5.5 \pm 0.4(*) n=3	0.95 \pm 0.08
	4-11 μm polymineral pIRIR ₂₉₀	15.9 \pm 0.3 n=9	15.2 \pm 0.3 n=3	1.05 \pm 0.03
	4-11 μm polymineral pIRIR ₂₂₅	14.5 \pm 0.1 n=8	17.2 \pm 0.1 n=3	0.84 \pm 0.01

(*) The L_x/T_x signal was calculated taking into account both L_x/T_x at 2500Gy and L_x/T_x at 5000 Gy signals.

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Table S9. Saturation characteristics for dose response curves up to 5000 Gy on BAT-1.19A using different test doses. Data was fitted with a sum of two saturating exponential function.

Test dose (Gy)	Test dose (% D _e)	D ₀₁ (Gy)	D ₀₂ (Gy)	(L _n /T _n)/(L _x /T _x) _{5000 Gy}
17	0.9	193 ± 32	764 ± 145	1.05 ± 0.02
200	11	160 ± 34	820 ± 83	0.95 ± 0.02
400	22	257 ± 45	1241 ± 277	0.92 ± 0.01
800	44	232 ± 38	1042 ± 135	0.89 ± 0.02

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Table S10. The effect of adding large doses on top of the naturally accrued dose for sample BAT-1.19A using SAR-OSL, pIRIR₂₂₅ and pIRIR₂₉₀ protocols. L_n/T_n represents the natural corrected OSL signal. L_n^*/T_n^* is the corrected luminescence signal measured after a known dose (3600 Gy) is given on top of the naturally accrued dose, for this old sample. L_x/T_x represents the normalised OSL signal obtained for a large regenerative dose (5000Gy) given after the L_n^*/T_n^* was measured. L_x/T_x -SAR represents the corrected luminescence signal for a regenerative dose of 5000 Gy measured in the SAR protocol.

Sample code	Protocol	Added dose	L_n/T_n	$(L_n/T_n)^*$	(L_x/T_x) SAR)	(L_x/T_x)	$(L_n/T_n) / (L_x/T_x)$ SAR)	$(L_n/T_n)^* / (L_x/T_x)$	$(L_n/T_n)^* / (L_n/T_n)$
BAT-1.19A	4-11 μ m quartz SAR-OSL	Nat+4500 Gy	10.2 \pm 0.2	19.3 \pm 0.3	17.3 \pm 0.4	20.4 \pm 0.4	0.59 \pm 0.02	0.95 \pm 0.02	1.90 \pm 0.02
	63-90 μ m quartz SAR-OSL	Nat+4650 Gy	5.2 \pm 0.2	4.9 \pm 0.4	5.2 \pm 0.5	4.8 \pm 0.3	1.00 \pm 0.10	1.03 \pm 0.11	0.96 \pm 0.08
	4-11 μ m polymineral pIRIR ₂₂₅	Nat+3600 Gy	14.4 \pm 0.1	19.5 \pm 0.5	17.2 \pm 0.1	17.7 \pm 0.2	0.84 \pm 0.01	1.10 \pm 0.03	1.35 \pm 0.03
	4-11 μ m polymineral pIRIR ₂₉₀	Nat+3600 Gy	16.4 \pm 0.4	19.8 \pm 0.8	17.2 \pm 0.2	15.2 \pm 0.3	1.08 \pm 0.03	1.15 \pm 0.05	1.20 \pm 0.04

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Table S11. Maximum corrected luminescence signals recorded in the SAR-OSL and post-IRIRSL protocols used and natural corrected luminescence signals for the samples BAT-1.12-BAT-1.19. The last column presents the ratio of the natural signal to signal obtained for the maximum dose given, used as an indication of the closeness of the signal to saturation.

Grain size	Sample code	L_n/T_n average	Maximum given dose (Gy)	L_x/T_x max	$(L_n/T_n)/(L_x/T_x$ 5000Gy)
4-11 μ m quartz	BAT 1.12*	7.01 \pm 0.09	5000	17.64 \pm 0.29	0.40 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.13A	7.57 \pm 0.13	5000		0.43 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.13B	8.15 \pm 0.07	5000		0.46 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.14A	7.99 \pm 0.10	5000		0.45 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.14B	8.50 \pm 0.07	5000		0.48 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.16	8.58 \pm 0.07	5000		0.49 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.17*	8.83 \pm 0.06	5000		0.50 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.19*	9.74 \pm 0.06	5000		0.55 \pm 0.01
63-90 μ m quartz	BAT 1.12*	4.93 \pm 0.09	2500+500	6.49 \pm 0.25	0.76 \pm 0.03
	BAT 1.13A	5.67 \pm 0.54	2500+500		0.87 \pm 0.09
	BAT 1.13B	5.57 \pm 0.32	2500+5000		0.86 \pm 0.06
	BAT 1.14A	5.25 \pm 0.25	2500+5000		0.81 \pm 0.05
	BAT 1.14B	5.21 \pm 0.31	2500+5000		0.80 \pm 0.06
	BAT 1.16	5.20 \pm 0.31	2500+5000		0.80 \pm 0.06
	BAT 1.17*	5.24 \pm 0.16	2500+5000		0.81 \pm 0.04
	BAT 1.19*	5.04 \pm 0.16	2500+5000		0.78 \pm 0.04
4-11 μ m polymineral pIRIR ₂₉₀	BAT 1.12*	11.16 \pm 0.12	5000	15.45 \pm 0.24	0.72 \pm 0.01
	BAT 1.13A	14.20 \pm 0.22	5000		0.92 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.13B	14.64 \pm 0.19	5000		0.95 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.14A	13.85 \pm 0.28	5000		0.90 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.14B	14.40 \pm 0.18	5000		0.93 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.16	14.94 \pm 0.26	5000		0.97 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.17*	13.87 \pm 0.14	5000		0.90 \pm 0.02
	BAT 1.19*	15.67 \pm 0.20	5000		1.01 \pm 0.02
4-11 μ m polymineral pIRIR ₂₂₅	BAT 1.12*	9.66 \pm 0.25	5000	16.01 \pm 0.64	0.60 \pm 0.03
	BAT 1.13A	13.66 \pm 0.18	5000		0.85 \pm 0.04
	BAT 1.13B	14.08 \pm 0.21	5000		0.88 \pm 0.04
	BAT 1.14A	12.73 \pm 0.12	5000		0.80 \pm 0.03
	BAT 1.14B	13.96 \pm 0.26	5000		0.87 \pm 0.04
	BAT 1.16	12.93 \pm 0.08	5000		0.81 \pm 0.03
	BAT 1.17*	11.54 \pm 0.25	5000		0.72 \pm 0.03
	BAT 1.19*	14.24 \pm 0.11	5000		0.89 \pm 0.04

* For the samples marked with *, L_n/T_n average represent the average normalised natural luminescence signal for the doublet samples.

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Sample preparation for alpha spectrometry

For each 0.5 g of dried homogenized 0.3 ml of ^{210}Po (an alpha energy of 4.979 MeV) tracer (with 100 mBq/ml activity) was added in order to determine the chemical yield. Acid digestion was carried out by using 10 ml of concentrated HNO_3 in three steps; each time the sample evaporated until near-dryness. The same procedure was repeated in the presence of HCl . To eliminate the organic matter, H_2O_2 was added. The samples were heated at a constant temperature of 150 °C. In order to eliminate the acids, 20 ml of distilled water was added and evaporated until near-dryness. The procedure was repeated three times. The ^{210}Po sources were prepared by spontaneous deposition on the surface of high Ni content stainless steel discs in HCl acid medium with 0.5-1 pH for 3 h at 85 °C. Interferences (Fe-ions) were eliminated by adding ascorbic acid for forming iron complexes (Begy et al., 2015).

Begy, R.C., Dumitru, O.A., Simon, H., Steopoaie, I., 2015. An improved procedure for the determination of Po-210 by alpha spectrometry in sediments samples from Danube Delta. *Journal of Radioanalytical and Nuclear Chemistry* 303, 2553-2557.

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Figure S1. The ratio between the ^{210}Pb and ^{226}Ra (^{214}Pb and ^{214}Bi peaks) concentration determined by gamma spectrometry. The solid line indicates the ideal value while with dashed line is represented the average value of the ratios measured for all samples (0.48 ± 0.03).

Figure S2. The ratio between ^{210}Pb concentration determined by gamma spectrometry and ^{210}Po measured by alpha spectrometry. The solid line represents the ideal value of the ratio whereas the dotted lines represent 10% deviation from unity.

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Figure S3. Representative sensitivity-corrected dose response curves constructed for sample BAT-1.10 using one aliquot of (A) fine (4-11 μm) quartz grains, (B) coarse (63-90 μm) quartz grains and (C) (D) polymineral fine (4-11 μm) grains. The sensitivity corrected natural signals is depicted as a star and a line indicates the equivalent dose. Recycling and IR depletion points are represented as an inverse triangle and up triangle, respectively. The inset show a typical decay curve of natural CW-OSL signal (open squares) in comparison to a regenerated signal (open circles) induced by a beta dose approximately equal with the equivalent dose and a calibration quartz signal (open triangles) in the case of quartz data, while for pIRIR₂₉₀ and pIRIR₂₂₅ data, natural signals are compared to regenerative signals.

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Figure S4. Equivalent dose dependence on preheat temperatures for fine quartz fraction from sample BAT-1.13B. A cutheat (test dose preheat) of 180 °C was employed.

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Figure S5. Results of the fading rate measurements on individual aliquots of 4-11 μm polymineral material and 4-11 μm and 63-90 μm quartz. (A-D) pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol on sample BAT-1.11, (E-H) pIRIR₂₂₅ protocol on sample BAT-1.19A, (I-L) pIRIR₂₉₀ protocol on sample BAT-1.11, (M-P) SAR-OSL protocol on sample BAT-1.11 using coarse quartz and (Q-S) SAR-OSL protocol on sample BAT-1.11 using fine quartz. The signals were read after a maximum delay of 14 days for sample BAT-1.11 while for sample BAT-1.19A the maximum delay was 2 days. The highest storage period was 21 days in the case of 4-11 μm quartz and 23 days for 63-90 μm quartz. A number of 4 consecutive prompt read-outs were carried out before signal measurement after delay and two consecutive prompts read-outs were added after different delays times. The signal intensity of the first instantaneous read-out is represented with filled symbols.

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Figure S6. Luminescence ages on quartz and polymineral fine grains. Ages obtained by assuming secular equilibrium between ^{222}Ra and ^{210}Pb are presented with open symbols while ages calculated using the measured concentration of ^{238}U (^{234}Th : 92.3 keV and 92.8 keV peaks) and ^{222}Ra (^{214}Pb : 351 keV and 295 keV peaks; ^{214}Bi : 609 keV peak) based on gamma spectrometry, and the concentration of ^{210}Pb determined by alpha spectrometry are represented with filled symbols, assuming present day degree of radioactive disequilibrium. The OSL ages given with half coloured symbols were calculated assuming radioactive equilibrium for half of the burial time while for the other half the concentration of ^{210}Pb was taken into account.

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Figure S7. Average values for the natural sensitivity corrected luminescence signals for all the investigated aliquots. Data for BAT-1.12, BAT-1.17 and BAT-1.19 represent the average of the doublet samples.

Figure S8. Glass shards identified in the a) upper tephra layer and b) lower tephra layer in L2 unit.